

EMPR / *Early Music Performance & Research*

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Editorial

This issue celebrates a number of things. Firstly—and perhaps most significantly—this issue (roughly) marks the twenty-fifth anniversary of this journal. It was in January 1999 that the first issue of *Early Music Performer* was released, edited by Christopher Goodwin, aiming to expand and improve NEMA's offering of 'learned yet popular articles that bring recent research into performance practice to the attention of performers'. This format superseded *NEMA News* and was initially to be published quarterly. (Much to this editor's horror; biannual is far more reasonable...)

One can draw parallels between the circumstances that brought about the advent of *Early Music Performer* and the more recent update to the journal under my editorship, whereby we have expanded the offering and tweaked the name. However, I hope we have retained the 'learned yet popular' remit as laid down by Peter Holman in 'NEMA: Past, Present, Future' that opened the first issue of *EMP*. This current issue, I feel, represents this particularly well, with a mix of discussions from both scholars and performers – borne out in great and interesting form in the articles they have contributed. This is particularly pertinent as we forge onwards into a new era for this journal, and for *NEMA* as a whole, as the way in which we operate membership and, indeed, our chairpersonship changes.

With anniversary party hats already firmly on our heads, we might also consider this a belatedly celebratory issue for the composer anniversaries which fell last year: the 400th anniversary of the deaths of William Byrd and Thomas Weelkes, as well as the 400th anniversary of the birth of John Playford. In the case of the latter, I feel that this needs particular additional attention, as I think most would agree, if they realised at all, that his anniversary year was overshadowed slightly by Byrd and Weelkes. To any English Early Modernist, the impact of Playford and his printing/publishing business, beginning in the 1650s, perhaps needs little note. However, the quantity of music, indeed many popular and idiomatically 'English' tunes which may still be heard today, which saw their printed debut in Playford collections is staggering – on par with, if not surpassing, the collecting work of Percy Grainger, Cecil Sharp, and Ralph Vaughan

Williams in the late-nineteenth and early-twentieth centuries.

When one thinks of attempts to combine early music with other musical genres, a few (successful) examples might pop to mind: The Hillard Ensemble combining the music of Cristóbal de Morales' 'Parce mihi, Domine' with jazz saxophone from Jan Garbarek in *Officium* (ECM New Series. ECM 1525. 1994.) I'm sure being among the most easily recalled. In a departure from some of the more regular content this journal has seen for the last twenty-five years, Jon Boden (Bellowhead) offers an article delving into the usage of Playford tunes in the contemporary folk scene from the perspective of a professional performer. This exploration of another successful pairing of seemingly disparate (superficially, at least) genres will, I hope, encourage further conversation and thought considering the myriad performance contexts for what we might consider more 'regular' early music fare.

The links to Playford continue as we turn back to look at Byrd in Katherine Butler's article, looking at his legacy in popular culture. Weelkes also has some airtime through a review of Chichester Cathedral's most recent disc release, reviewed by Nancy Hadden. And, for those who might feel Byrd-ed out from last year's celebrations, we have some exceptional new insights from Olive Baldwin & Thelma Wilson, and Peter Holman looking at Josias Priest, Henry Purcell, and William Croft.

I hope that the offerings presented in this current issue reflect the ways in which the journal remains a thriving nexus for the 'learned yet popular' a quarter-century on from its inception as *Early Music Performer*, and that in another twenty-five years, one of my successors will be as equally able to make the same claim.

Samuel Teague

July 2024

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‘Honest Jo. Priest’ and his School in Chelsea

Olive Baldwin & Thelma Wilson

In 1712 a letter was written for the *Spectator* but not used. It was finally published in 1725, in the first of the two volumes of *Original and Genuine Letters sent to The Tatler and Spectator During the Time those Works were publishing. None of which have been before Printed*. The letter, signed ‘The Wagg’, told of a supposed wedding party:

The bride was a pretty blooming beauty, who having been bred at honest Jo. Priest’s school in Chelsea, had invited a fine sample of her school-fellows to be witnesses of her happiness. . . . the ladies, who had not met together since the opera they all perform’d in at school, were pitying the late misfortunes of their poor master, and praising the goodness of their mistress; seeming very much rejoiced when I acquainted them Mr. Priest had got through all his troubles, was beginning the world again in a very handsom, airy house in Lawrence-street in Chelsea, had got many scholars, and was in hopes of many more.¹

The writing of the letter can be securely dated to spring 1712, as we are told that the bride was a great admirer of the actress Lucretia Bradshaw, whose theatre benefit was on ‘this present Monday the 12th of May’, when she acted in *Caius Marius*. Her benefit was indeed on that day in 1712, when she was advertised for the role of Lavinia in Otway’s tragedy.² It seems that readers of the *Spectator* were expected to know something about Jo Priest, his school at Chelsea and his recent troubles. The phrase ‘Honest Jo Priest’ was not assuring the readers that Priest did not steal or over-charge his pupils, but that he was an old performer who was popular and well known. A similar case is the singer Richard Leveridge who, after he retired at the age of 80, was called ‘honest Dick Leveridge, the Father of the English Stage’.³

Priest’s boarding school for young ladies in Chelsea is of course known to music historians as the venue for the performance of John Blow’s *Venus and Adonis* in April 1684, when Priest’s daughter sang Adonis, and of Henry Purcell’s *Dido and Aeneas* a few years later. This letter gives an unexpected insight into the later history of Josias Priest and his school. The young ladies at the supposed wedding cannot have been in one of these performances more than 20 years earlier, so there must have been a fairly recent opera or masque performed at the school of which nothing is known nowadays.

Research into Priest’s career has been bedevilled by the different interpretations of the familiar name, ‘Jo’. His actual name was Josias, for that was how he signed the notice of his school’s removal from Leicester Fields to Chelsea in 1680⁴, but we find him called Josiah, Joseph and, even, on one occasion each, Jonas and John. His wife Frances was sometimes called Frank, Franck or Fran, and signed herself as Francke in bills for parents of pupils at the Chelsea school.⁵ It seems almost certain that the couple can be traced first in the City of London parish of St Mary le Bow, and that they afterwards moved progressively westwards to the parishes of St Andrew Holborn, St Martin-in-the-Fields and finally Chelsea, where Mrs Frank Priest was buried on 20 April 1733 and Mr Josias Priest on 1 January 1735. Their marriage date is unknown (there are no surviving marriage registers of St Mary le Bow for this period), but two daughters were baptised there:

Child	Father	Baptised	Buried
Frances	Josiah Priest	18 May 1665	25 July 1666 as daughter of Joseph
Katherine	Joseph Preist	19 June 1666	

Table 1 - Baptisms and burials at St Mary le Bow

¹ *Original and Genuine Letters sent to The Tatler and Spectator During the Time those Works were publishing. None of which have been before Printed* (London, 1725), vol.1, 14-17.

² *Daily Courant*, 12 May 1712.

³ *London Evening Post*, 22-24 October 1751.

⁴ *London Gazette*, 22-25 November 1680.

⁵ Jennifer Thorp, ‘Dance in late 17th-century London: Priestly muddles’, *Early Music*, 26 (1998), 203 contains a reproduction of the bill.

The parish clerk of St Mary le Bow did not record mothers' names, but the fact that the first daughter was called Frances suggests that Priest was already married to Frances or Francke. It is in these registers that we first encounter two of the versions of Jo Priest's first name. Josiah, of which Josias is a variant, is the biblical name of one of the kings of Judah, and Joseph could well have been a misinterpretation of a note made at the christenings and written up later. Katherine would have been seventeen in April 1684 when *Venus and Adonis* was staged at the Chelsea school, and she must have been the singer of Adonis, for the Priests' only other surviving daughters were then eight years old or younger.

The 'late misfortunes' referred to in the *Spectator* letter can scarcely have been as serious as those the young couple encountered in their early married life. Frances was born and baptised in the City of London in the ghastly plague year of 1665, and her burial took place only six weeks before the Great Fire of London, which began on 2 September 1666. St Mary le Bow was one of the 87 churches that were destroyed, along with most of the rest of the City. After the Fire, the family moved westwards to the parish of St Andrew Holborn, and five children had been baptised there by March 1675. The registers here are much more helpful to music and dance historians, as can be seen in this transcript of the baptism of Thomas, who was to become a dancing master like his father:

[March 1671] Tho: Preest son of Josias dancing master & of Frances his wife born in his house in Fetter Lane behind Mr Bluers & was bapt^d ye 12th.

Thomas was the only child born to the Priests in Fetter Lane to survive to adulthood

Table 2 gives the details of the five children that were baptised there, showing the father as Josias or Josiah and the mother as Frances, Frank or Franck. The boy Francis must have died before 3 May 1677 because another Francis, who was to live for less than two weeks, was born to Josias and Frances on

that date, when the family was living in the parish of St Martin in the Fields.⁶

Child	Father	Mother	Baptism	Burial
Josiah	Gosiah	Frances	25 October 1668	31 March 1692 (as Josias) ⁷
Tho.	Josias	Frances	12 March 1671	
Franck	Josias	Franck	2 March 1673	10 March 1673
Francis	Josiah	Franck	29 December 1673	before 3 May 1677
Mary	Josias	Frank	14 March 1675	1 April 1675

Table 2 - Baptisms and burials at St Andrew Holborn

As well as being known as a teacher of dancing, Priest was also achieving success as a dancer on the stage, and the move to Fetter Lane brought him closer to the London theatres. The first record of him as a theatre dancer comes from *Roscicus Anglicanus*, written by the theatre prompter John Downes and published in 1708. He wrote that Dryden's 1667 comedy *Sir Martin Marall* at the Duke's Theatre was 'Crown'd with an Excellent Entry: In the last Act at the Mask, by Mr. Priest and Madam Davies'.⁸ The young singer and dancer Mary (Moll) Davies was soon to be taken off the stage by Charles II to become one of his long-term mistresses. She sang Venus, with her daughter by the king as Cupid, in the first performance of *Venus and Adonis*, which took place before the king in 1683. It is very likely that Priest was called on to dance on that occasion and possibly to arrange the dances, and that this led to the production of the piece at his Chelsea school a year later.

Theatre notices are almost non-existent at this time, but Priest clearly remained a useful theatre dancer, for we know that in 1673 he was involved in a spectacular production put on by the Duke's Company at the new Dorset Garden Theatre. Downes reported:

The *Tragedy of Macbeth*, alter'd by Sir William Davenant; being drest in all it's Finery, as new Cloath's, new Scenes, Machines, as flyings for the Witches; with

⁶ Names were sometimes latinised in the baptismal registers of St Martin in the Fields and this baby was recorded as 'Franciscus'.

⁷ The Chelsea registers show a Josias Priest buried there on 31 March 1692.

⁸ John Downes, *Roscicus Anglicanus, or an Historical Review of the Stage*, ed. Judith Milhous and Robert D. Hume (London, 1987), 62-3.

all the Singing and Dancing in it: The first Compos'd by Mr. *Lock*, the other by Mr. *Channell*⁹ and Mr. *Joseph Priest*; it being all Excellently perform'd being in the nature of an Opera. It Recompens'd double the Expence; it proves still a lasting Play.¹⁰

Downes named 'Mr Jo Priest' as the choreographer of Purcell's dramatic opera *King Arthur* in 1691 and we know that it was Josias Priest who was involved in *The Fairy Queen* in 1692, for in Bray's *Country Dances* (1699) the music for the 'Dance of the Followers of Night' in Act 2 of *The Fairy Queen*, is headed 'An Entry by the late Mr. *Henry Purcel*, the Dance compos'd by Mr. *Josias Preist*'.¹¹ It therefore seems that, in his report of *Macbeth*, Downes was interpreting 'Jo' as 'Joseph', and that the stage dancer was the Josias Priest of Chelsea who featured in the *Spectator* letter of 1712.

In February 1675, shortly before the birth and death of his last child to be baptised at St Andrew Holborn, Priest was involved in a very prestigious occasion at Court, the performances of the masque *Calisto*, with the young princesses and future queens, Mary and Anne, in leading roles.¹² In October that year 'John Preist' was paid the large sum of one hundred pounds by the Exchequer 'for his services in the late ballet'.¹³ He was not listed as one of the twelve professional dancers, many of whom were French, so his contribution may have been to choreograph and rehearse dances for the noble amateurs who were such an import part of the production. Moll Davis was an important participant in *Calisto*, where her 'graceful motions and admirable singing' as the River Thames and the shepherdess Sylvia were praised by the author John Crowne in his 'To the Reader', printed with the text.

By early 1676 Priest's professional success and the money from his work on *Calisto* enabled him to

move his family further west to a more fashionable area, Leicester Fields. This was the ward of the parish of St Martin in the Fields where Leicester Square was being developed with high class residences. The register entries for the four children born here give only parents' names (variously Josias or Josiah and Frances, Fran or Frank), so we do not know exactly where they lived. We do know, however, that by 1680 the Priests were running a boarding school for young gentlewomen and that this was a success, for that November they were able to move still further west, to the attractive and well-to-do village of Chelsea. Priest announced the move in the *London Gazette* of 22-25 November 1680:

Josias Priest, Dancing-Master, that kept a Boarding-School for Gentlewomen in *Leicester Fields*, is removed to the great School-House at *Chelsey*, which was Mr. *Portmans*, where he did Teach, there will continue the same Masters, and others, to the Improvement of the said School.

In John Bowack's *The Antiquities of Middlesex*, published in 1705, Chelsea was praised for the: 'Sweetness of its Air, and Pleasant Situation ... where a Man may perfectly enjoy the Pleasures of Country and City together'. It was said to contain 'Schools with a great Number of Boarders, especially Young Ladies'.¹⁴ This book was published twenty-five years after the Priests moved to Chelsea, and its short paragraph on the school contains another interpretation of 'Jo':

At the West end of the Town near the Countess of *Lindseys*, is a large spacious House, the Building somewhat Old, formerly the Seat of the Worthy Family of the *Gorges*, in which for many Years past has been kept a famous Boarding School for young Ladies, by Mr. *Jonas Priest*.¹⁵

⁹ Luke Channell was sworn in as the dancing master of the Duke's Company in November 1664, see Judith Milhous and Robert D. Hume, *A Register of English Theatrical Documents 1660-1737* (Carbondale and Edwardsville, 1991), 39.

¹⁰ Downes, 33.

¹¹ Thomas Bray, *Country Dances* (London, 1699), 17 (no. 16). Copy at the Vaughan Williams Memorial Library, Cecil Sharp House, London (QS.35.3).

¹² John Crowne, *Calisto: or, The Chaste Nymph. The Late Masque at Court, As it was frequently Presented there, by several Persons of Great Quality* (London, 1675).

¹³ Eleanore Boswell, *The Restoration Court Stage 1660-1702* (London, 1932), 225.

¹⁴ John Bowack, *The Antiquities of Middlesex* (London, 1705), part 1, 15.

¹⁵ Bowack, 15.

Bowack lived in Church Lane, Chelsea. He must have known Priest, and his use of 'Jonas' may be further evidence that Josias was known by his acquaintances as Mr Jo Priest. Gorges House was a typical Elizabethan gabled mansion and would have had a great hall suitable for balls and operas, and plenty of rooms and gardens for the young lady boarders. It was close to the Thames, but its view of the river was cut off by Lindsey House, which had been built six years before the Priests moved to Chelsea. *Venus and Adonis* was not the first musical piece put on at Gorges House, for in 1676 the masque *Beauties Triumph*, with a libretto by Thomas Duffett was staged at the house:

'Presented by the Scholars of Mr. Jeffery Banister and Mr. James Hart, At their *New BOARDING-SCHOOL* for Young Ladies and Gentlewomen kept in that House which was formerly Sir *Arthur Gorges*, at CHELSEY'.¹⁶

Dancing was a central part of the education of young ladies at both day and boarding schools, so it is not surprising that a celebrated dancer and his wife should run a successful and long-lasting school. We are indebted to the papers of the Verney family of Claydon House, Buckinghamshire for some insights into Priest's school in the 1680s.¹⁷ Eight year-old Mary Verney was the daughter of Edmund Verney, the oldest son of Sir Ralph Verney. After she became a boarder at the Chelsea school in August 1683, her relations wrote to each other about the annual 'Grand Balls' which they attended each spring from 1684 to 1687. at 'Mrs Priest's school at Great Chelsey'. In April 1684 John Verney wrote, 'My niece is well and this day she is to show her art and skill in Dancing in the Grand Ball' and after the event he wrote: 'We were both at the Ball & opera last Thursday, where we saw my neece dance & act some part in it, and truly she doth it very well'.¹⁸

The opera was *Venus and Adonis* and John Verney's annotations on his copy of the libretto tell us that 'last Thursday' was the seventeenth of April 1684, and that Priest's daughter played Adonis.¹⁹ Priest would have organised the dances and probably danced as a hunter at the end of Act 1 in the school performance. The young Mary Verney was presumably one of the chorus of cupids who dance and sing, and there were also dances of shepherds, shepherdesses and Graces that were suitable for the older girls. The Verney family letters about the Grand Balls in the spring of the next three years do not mention an opera, but always comment approvingly on Molly's dancing. Unfortunately, she left the school before the performance of *Dido and Aeneas*.

Henry Purcell had been working in the London theatre from at least 1680, when he composed a scene of religious ritual and several songs for Nathaniel Lee's *Theodosius*. After this he continued to compose songs for the theatre, so Priest would clearly have known him. Bryan White's researches into letters of the Aleppo merchant, Rowland Sherman, show convincingly that *Dido and Aeneas* was composed for Priest's school. Before he left England in 1688, Sherman had been in an amateur group that played music with Purcell, and he wrote back home from Aleppo: 'If Harry has sett to the Harpsechord the Symphony of the mask he made for Preists Ball, I should be very glad of a copy of it'.²⁰ *Dido and Aeneas* was certainly suited to a school that prided itself on its dance teaching, for the opera and its allegorical prologue call for seventeen dances. The music lessons at the school appear to have included instruction in the guitar, a fashionable instrument for ladies, for the libretto of *Dido and Aeneas* calls for 'A Dance Gittars Chacony' in Act 1 and 'Gitter Ground a Dance' in Act 2.

It seems that not all the parents approved of this elaborate operatic production. In the spring of

¹⁶ Wm. Barclay Squire, 'Beauties Triumph at Mr. Priest's School', *Musical Times*, 47 (1906), 250. The performance was four years before Priest moved to Gorges House. Barclay Squire lists three songs from the piece, and the libretto is available in Eighteenth Century Collections Online. Banister was a violinist and Hart a singer, As their school was new in 1676 and Priest took over in 1780, their establishment was short lived. For the careers of Banister and Hart, see Andrew Ashbee and David Lasocki, *A Biographical Dictionary of English Court Musicians 1485-1714* (Aldershot, 1998), vol. 1, 63-5; 550-51.

¹⁷ M. M. Verney, *Memoirs of the Verney Family* (London, 1899), vol. 4.

¹⁸ Bryan White, 'Letter from Aleppo: dating the Chelsea School performance of *Dido and Aeneas*', *Early Music*, 37 (2009), 421-2.

¹⁹ The libretto is reproduced in Richard Luckett, 'A new source for *Venus and Adonis*', *Musical Times*, 130 (1989), 76-9.

²⁰ White, 419.

1691, a Mrs Buck was looking for a suitable school for her friend's daughter, and she reported:

Preists att Little Chelsey was one which was much commended; but he hath lately had an Opera which I'me sure hath done him a great injury; & the Parents of the Children not satisfied with so Publick a show.²¹

Purcell's music and Priest's connections with the stage must surely have led to the presence in the audience of theatrical people, which could have disturbed some parents. Mrs Buck added 'Att present all schoolls are redicul'd; they have latly made a Play cal'd The Boarding School'. The play was Thomas D'Urfey's *Love for Money; or, The Boarding School*, premiered at Drury Lane early in 1691, and it must have been particularly annoying to Priest, for the play's painted scenery set it in Chelsea, and D'Urfey had written an epilogue for the school's *Dido and Aeneas*. In the play, the dancing and music masters Coopee and Semibrief run off with and marry 'Two tawdry Hoyden overgrown Romps of the Boarding School'. Lady Addleplot, the mother of one of them, comments: 'This comes of putting Girls to a Boarding School', and her husband Nicompoop adds 'Ay, they hop and dance till they set their blood on fire and then they quench it with the next puddle they come at'.²² In his preface to the text, D'Urfey admitted that at the premiere the play was hooted at by 'My hissing Antagonists of the *Nimble Craft*', but claimed that the satire was only general. The play proved popular and must have adversely affected the Chelsea schools for a time.

It was after Purcell's work with Priest on *Dido and Aeneas* that London's one theatre company, the United Company, began to produce dramatic operas with extended musical scenes composed by Purcell, *The Prophetess; or, the History of Dioclesian* in 1690, *King Arthur* in 1691 and *The Fairy Queen* in 1692. For all three works, Downes wrote that the

dances were made by Mr Priest, and Priest almost certainly danced in these multi-media spectaculars. Downes refers only to 'Mr Priest', but as we know that it was 'Mr. Josias Preist' who was involved in *The Fairy Queen*, it does seem that Josias was the choreographer and dancer.²³

What, then, was happening at Chelsea while Priest was doing all this work for the London stage? The answer, of course, is that Franck Priest was managing the school, as can be seen in the references to 'Mrs Priest's School' in the Verney papers. Some time ago we were in contact with Amanda Eubanks Winkler, who was working on music in 17th century boarding schools in Hackney and elsewhere, and she replied:

I have encountered no female dance teachers in my research. But oftentimes women ran the business end of the establishment (doing the bills, etc.) and hired a series of male teachers (dance, music, etc.) to come in to give instruction.²⁴

Indeed, a bill from the Verney archive shows that it was 'Francke Priest' who issued and signed the bills for the school at Chelsea. The charge for board and schooling was £5 for a quarter, and the bill also lists money owing for music and singing, as well as for shoes, gloves and a card of pins. The lack of an extra charge for dancing implies that it was part of the basic curriculum.²⁴ £20 a year plus extras made up a considerable sum and by February 1688 Mary Verney's father could not pay Mrs Priest the £20 he owed her.

The school was listed as 'Mrs Priest's' in several issues of *A Collection for the Improvement of Husbandry and Trade* between August 1694 and October 1695.²⁵ Franck Priest must have been a very strong woman, both physically and mentally. Besides all the challenges of overseeing a boarding school, it seems that she gave birth to seven more children at

²¹ Mark Goldie, 'The earliest notice of Purcell's *Dido and Aeneas*', *Early Music*, 20 (1992), 393.

²² Thomas Durfey, *Love for Money: or, The Boarding School* (London, 1691), 65.

²³ Bray, 17 (no. 16). David Falconer, in 'The Two Mr Priests of Chelsea', *Musical Times*, 128 (1987), 263, assumes that the dancer Josias Priest was buried at Chelsea on 2 March 1692, a clear impossibility as the premiere of *The Fairy Queen* was not until 2 May 1692. In fact the burial was on 31 March and must have been that of Priest's oldest son, aged 13.

²⁴ Thorp, 203.

²⁵ We are very grateful to Jennifer Thorp for alerting us to this publication.

Chelsea between 1682 and 1693, the last when she must have been in her mid-forties. Only three of these children born in Chelsea survived childhood. In a letter of 5 May 1684 John Verney wrote: 'Mrs Priest the Schoolmistress on Saturday last had a little girl (one of her daughters) drowned in a Tub of Water and very little water there was to do it'. Sir Ralph Verney replied, 'Such little children should never be left alone'.²⁶ The only Priest to be buried in Chelsea at this time was Susanna, who was baptised on 28 March 1682 and buried on 12 May 1684. Like the other six Priest children baptised at Chelsea, the registers give only the father's name, as Joseph Priest. Understandably, this had led to the suggestion that the father of these children was not the man who had moved his school to Chelsea. However, we know that Josias Priest's wife was Franke and that the 'Schoolmistress' was Franke Priest, for it was she who she signed the Verney bills at Chelsea. This means that either the Joseph of the baptismal registers was in fact Josias or that Verney was mistaken about the mother of the child. As John Verney's niece was at the school at the time and he took a close interest in her education, such a mistake about the child's identity is very unlikely. The girls at the school must have known who the child's mother was. It seems that the writer of the Chelsea baptismal registers preferred to use the more familiar name of Joseph, or misinterpreted the notes from which the registers were written up. The Chelsea registers record no Joseph anywhere other than in these baptismal registers, and Chelsea rates were paid by Josias, and later also by Thomas Priest for his own house. It is interesting that in a later generation there was another 'Josias Priest', whose relationship to our dancer is unknown, and his name suffered similar variations. Josiah Priest was a boy at the Chapel Royal, leaving it in 1706.²⁷ He became an organist and in 1724 the subscription list to the first book of Richard Neal's *Pocket Companion for Gentlemen and Ladies* included 'Mr. Josias Priest,

Organist of ye Abby Ch. at Bath,' and in the same year the subscription list for William Croft's *Musica Sacra* included 'Mr Joseph Priest, Organist of Bath'.

We know very little about what Priest was doing on the London stage in the mid and late 1690s, for there is no way of finding out what was happening on most evenings in the theatre. In 1694 tensions in London's United Theatre Company came to a head and many of the leading actors formed a breakaway company that moved to a theatre in Lincoln's Inn Fields. John Downes went as prompter with the rebels and so makes no further reference to Priest in *Roscicus Anglicanus*, for Priest remained with Henry Purcell and the patent company that performed at Drury Lane and Dorset Gardens. It would seem that Priest was involved in the dramatic opera *The Indian Queen*, premiered not long before Purcell died in November 1695, for Bray's *Country Dances* of 1699 contains a tune from Act 3 of *The Indian Queen* headed 'An Entry by the late Mr. Hen. Purcell, the Dance Compos'd by Mr. Priest'.²⁸ Priest was still with the patent company in February 1699, for he danced in *The Island Princess*, a very successful dramatic opera with music by Daniel Purcell, Jeremiah Clarke and Richard Leveridge.²⁹ He performed an entrée in Act 2³⁰ and also as the old miser in the winter section of the final masque, *The Four Seasons, or Love in every Age*³¹, where the playtext reads: 'Enter a Dutch-woman with a Stove warming her self, her Cloaths lin'd with Furs. An Old Miser makes Love to her in a dance'.³² By 1699 Priest had been dancing on the London stage for over 30 years. He may even have made some later appearances, for the *Spectator* letter's 'Honest Jo Priest' implies that in 1712 he was still remembered as a personality.

It was in 1712 that John Weaver published *An Essay towards an History of Dancing* and had high praise for Priest in his section on grotesque dancing. He wrote:

²⁶ Thorp, 202-4.

²⁷ Andrew Ashbee and David Lasocki, *A Biographical Dictionary of English Court Musicians 1485-1714* (Aldershot, 1998), vol. 2, 920.

²⁸ Bray, *Country Dances*, 23 (no.14).

²⁹ For the date of the premiere, see *The Island Princess*, intro. Curtis A. Price and Robert D. Hume (Music for London Entertainment, Tunbridge Wells, 1985), vii-x.

³⁰ 'An Entre Danc'd by Mr Priest in ye Island Princess', given in *The Island Princess*, intro. Price and Hume, xix.

³¹ Bray, 25 (no.15), headed 'Chacone, the Dance compos'd by Mr. Preist'. The music is that for the dance of the Dutch woman and the miser.

³² Peter Motteux, *The Island Princess, or the Generous Portuguese. Made into an Opera* (London 1701), 43.

Grotesque Dancing is wholly calculated for the Stage, and takes in the greatest Part of *Opera-Dancing*, and is much more difficult than the *Serious*, requiring the utmost Skill of the Performer. ... Mr. *Joseph Priest* of *Chelsea*, I take to have been the greatest Master of this kind of Dancing, that has appear'd on our Stage'.³³

During the 1699-1700 season Weaver, who had just moved to London, danced with the Drury Lane company, and so would have taken part in performances of *The Island Princess* and encountered 'Jo Priest' in his late maturity. In 1711, 'Mr Priest, Senior, of Chelsea' had subscribed, among other leading dancing masters, to Edmund Pemberton's *An Essay for the further Improvement of Dancing*, which included a minuet for twelve ladies by 'Mr: Preist', clearly a useful item for pupils in the display section of a dancing school ball.³⁴

So, what were the 'late misfortunes of their poor master' which distressed the young ladies? We can only speculate. Priest's son Thomas had become a dancing master living in Chelsea and was presumably helping with the school, but Thomas's wife died in childbirth, for both she and their daughter were buried at Chelsea on 4 March 1710, two days after the baby was baptised. This family tragedy must have affected the school. At this time, there also seems to have been a trend for the higher echelons of society to have their daughters educated at home by visiting masters, rather than sending them away to school. Certainly Mrs Buck, the lady worried about the 'public show', approved of this. One of Priest's troubles in 1712 may well have been the condition of Gorge's House, which had been described as a 'Building somewhat Old' by John Bowack in 1705. By 1712 the Priests had been there for over thirty years, and the upkeep of the many roofs and gutters and the state of the interior could well have been neglected for too long. Jennifer Thorp's archival research has shown

that the rates on Gorges house declined from 1704 onwards, with a sudden reduction in August 1711.³⁵ The house was demolished in the 1720s. Priest's move to the 'very handsom, airy house in Lawrence-street in Chelsea' is confirmed by the rate books that show he left Gorges House and moved to nearby Lawrence Street, where he paid rates between January 1712 and Michaelmas 1714. After the Priests left this house, the widow of the Duke of Monmouth lived there, and it became known as Monmouth House. By autumn 1714 the Priests must have been ready for retirement, although of course he could have continued to give dancing lessons. They both lived to a good age, for 'Mrs Frank Priest' was buried in Chelsea on 20 April 1733 and 'Mr Josias Priest' was buried there on 1 January 1735. It is perhaps worthy of note that the Chelsea burial registers at this period only attach the social signifiers 'Mr and 'Mrs' to a small number of the adults buried there.

Finally, what was the opera in which the young ladies had all performed, which readers of the *Spectator* in 1712 seem to have been expected to have known about? By this time opera in London had come to mean all-sung works in Italian, with small casts of highly skilled and very expensive stars, and with dancing only as entr'acte entertainments, so it cannot have been one of these works that was performed at the school. A masque from one of the English dramatic operas from the 1690s is possible, or a recent work that did not get performed in the theatre, like Daniel Purcell's *Masque of Orpheus and Euridice* of which the music is lost.³⁶ Alternatively, did Priest revive *Venus and Adonis* or *Dido and Aeneas*? If *Dido and Aeneas* had been his commission, he would presumably have retained the music. (Only one number from it appeared in *Orpheus Britannicus*, the collection organised by Purcell's widow and published in 1698.) In 1700 *Dido and Aeneas* had resurfaced as four entertainments inserted into a production of *Measure for Measure* mounted by Thomas Betterton's

³³ John Weaver, *An Essay Towards an History of Dancing, In which the whole Art and its Various Excellencies are in some Measure explain'd* (London, 1712), 164-6.

³⁴ Edward Pemberton, *An Essay for the further Improvement of Dancing, Being a Collection of Figure Dances* (London, 1711). Josias would have been 'Mr Priest, Senior' because his son Thomas was now also working as a dancing master.

³⁵ Thorp, 204-5.

³⁶ *The Muses Mercury* of January 1707 reported that the masque was ready and Daniel Purcell's music 'on this occasion, is very much commended'. The libretto, by John Dennis, was printed in the February 1707 issue, pp.29-35. Some adaptation and the inclusion of dances would have been needed to make it suitable for performance at Priest's school.

company at Lincoln's Inn Fields. Did Betterton remember the original performance and ask Priest for a copy of the music, or was he reminded of the opera because Priest had mounted it again? Alternatively, Priest could have decided to stage the opera again after it was used at Lincoln's Inn Fields. The young ladies could even have been singing in a new English masque of which all trace is lost, for the *Venus and Adonis* libretto that linked Blow's little opera to the school performance only emerged in a miscellaneous collection purchased by Cambridge University Library in 1987.³⁷

Olive Baldwin & Thelma Wilson

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Figure 1 - 'Mr. Joseph Priest, Organist of Bath' in the list of subscribers for William Croft, Musica Sacra (London: John Walsh, 1724). (Public Domain, IMSLP)

37 Luckett, 76-9.

Playing with Playford

The English Dancing Master & the English Folk Scene

Jon Boden

John Playford's *The English Dancing Master* (1651) is a point of intersection between early music and the contemporary English folk scene. The melodies it records feature in the early music canon as some of the more modern material regularly performed, and in the English folk scene as the most archaic. For the Early music specialist, Playford marks the end of the process of evolution from Elizabethan courtly dance music towards country dance tunes 'for the masses'; for the folk musician it is a window into the genesis of modern folk music. The material is equally at home in either camp, but the musical interpretations are conditioned by the conventions and instincts of each genre's stylistic mien.

I am a folk musician and have been playing and arranging Playford tunes alongside more modern instrumental folk music for twenty-five years. In this article I will consider the ways in which Playford's English Dancing Master repertoire is used within the English Folk Scene. The guiding assumption in writing this is that all approaches (from period-accurate to synth-pop) are valid and interesting treatments of an important body of melody preserved for us by the efforts of John Playford. It is beyond the scope of this article (and beyond the knowledge and skill-set of the author) to go into any detail about the various musical approaches to Playford within the early music movement. The aim here instead is to present an overview of the ways in which the folk scene utilises Playford's oeuvre within the broader body of folk repertoire, in the hope that it will be of interest to readers coming at it from the early music end of things.

Individual playing style is a huge part of the artistic bedrock of the folk scene that runs in parallel to the regional stylistic tropes of the various traditions.

There is a slight tension between these two stylistic lodestars. On the one hand originality and inimitability are highly prized and the sense that one player is copying another too slavishly is very much looked down upon. On the other hand, the concept of a definable regional style is also highly valued. Either way it is a feature of the English folk scene in particular that players are often striving to define their 'own sound,' whether within an existing stylistic tradition or outside it, and it is this dynamic that informs their stylistic approach to Playford, rather than any historical considerations. Regional and individual style is based upon a number of characteristics that will be employed in varying degrees by each player.

Swing is a musical term normally associated with jazz, but it is a huge feature in traditional music, particularly with bowed and free reed instruments. Different regional styles and different individual players will use swing to varying degrees, but it is always significantly less pronounced, less definite, and less constant than jazz swing. Amongst English-style folk players, swing is sometimes referred to as 'swagger' and this is perhaps a more useful way of thinking about it. It is a musical impulse that toys with the rhythmical assumptions of particular metres – a 9/8 jig leans into 4/4, a straight 4/4 leans into a dotted 4/4, a waltz leans towards two beats in the bar. It uses listeners' expectations of where the beat(s) should be landing and plays with those assumptions, delaying some notes, hastening others, and in so doing creates tension and release, rhythmic dissonance followed by resolution.

The king-of-swing in English folk fiddle is a man who actually saw himself as a Scottish fiddler, but whose highly individual, anarchic style was mostly employed in English bands and as accompaniment to English singers, generating a huge impact on the development of English fiddle style. Dave Swarbrick (1941-2016) recorded several Playford

melodies and his stately rendition of Dr Isaacs Maggot on his album *Flittin* gives many examples of folk swagger in a seventeenth-century tune.

The use of **implied syncopation** is a close companion of swing/swagger. In jig time ($\frac{6}{8}$) most contemporary folk performers will tend to emphasise beats 3 and 6, whereas most early music performers tend to emphasise beats 1 and 4. In $\frac{4}{4}$ tunes most contemporary folk performers will tend to emphasise beats 2 and 4, or at least do more so than their early music counterparts.

A subtle and effective demonstration of this technique is Leveret's 2019 recording of 'Cuckolds All Awry'. Andy Cutting (melodeon) executes much of the implied syncopation, as can be seen from the transcription in example 1.

However, Cutting's actual performance is far more subtle than it is possible to represent in transcription as it is constantly varying in emphasis. In addition, the fiddle (Sam Sweeney) and English concertina (Rob Harbron) tend not to *emphasise* these syncopated beats per se, but instead to play off the melodeon 'groove.' The combination of the (subtly) syncopated melodeon with the not-quite syncopated fiddle and concertina is beguiling and exciting, without allowing the syncopation to overpower the tune.

Of course, there is plenty of syncopation in the Playford tunes themselves, for example in the penultimate bar of 'Cuckolds All Awry', see example 2, but this melodic syncopation is a slightly different type to the implied, emphasis-based syncopation of the folk player. Paradoxically the melodic syncopation of the Playford melodies is very unusual in more modern folk repertoire, at least up until the late twentieth century when tunes such as Catharsis by Amy Cann became very popular and influential.

Padding notes are another element of English folk approaches to Playford's music, exemplified by Leveret (see example 3). Rather than playing the tune as written, Habron, Cutting, and Sweeney instead tend to break long notes down into quavers and pad out the melody with pedal notes or improvised linking passages, getting progressively more elaborate as the tune repeats (transposed to G for reference to the above).

Padding notes and implied syncopation are complementary techniques allowing the folk player to diverge from the written Playford melody without ever fully contradicting it. In extreme cases syncopation and adding notes can turn a tune into something more akin to twentieth-century composed syncopated folk tune, as in Bellowhead's version of 'Childgrove' – the original version and the Bellowhead version can be compared in examples 4 & 5.

Example 1 - Transcription of implied syncopation in 'Cuckolds all awry' as performed by Leveret (2019).

Example 2 - 'Cuckolds all a Row', printed in Playford, *The English Dancing Master* (London: T. Harper, 1651), 67 (Public Domain, *IMSLP*)

Example 3 - 'Cuckolds all awry' with padding notes, as played by Leveret (2019)

Ornamentation is one of the key determiners of regional style within the modern folk scene, particularly amongst fiddle-players. The use of a fingered roll to imitate a triplet, for example, is particularly characteristic of Irish styles, whereas the use of bowed triplets is more associated with Scottish fiddle styles. In most cases these regional styles are fluid, and the modern player will be rooted in one regional style but will use a range of ornaments and other stylistic tropes in the service of defining their own individual style.

English fiddle is slightly different because, unlike Irish and Scottish regional styles, it was left more or less fallow throughout the first half of the twentieth century and so failed to solidify stylistically. To the extent that ornamented English fiddle style can be said to exist at all, it is a modern

invention. Dave Swarbrick has already been mentioned as key in this process. Other fiddlers of his generation (Barry Dransfield, Peter Knight) who played on the English scene also contributed but (like Swarbrick) didn't view themselves as specifically English fiddlers. It was not until the 1990s that the stylistic evolution of English fiddle-playing was solidified. The first of a new generation was Chris Wood, who came to English fiddle via Quebecois and Swedish music and fully embraced it in the band *The English Acoustic Collective* whose 2004 album *Ghosts* included the Playford tunes 'Hare's Maggot' and 'Mr Isaac's Maggot', with two fiddles (Wood & John Dipper) plus Rob Harbron on English concertina. All three players were clearly influenced by Swedish traditional ornamentation as can be seen in their approach to ornamenting 'Mr Isaac's Maggot' (example 6).

Example 4 - 'Childgrove' as found in Henry Playford, *The Dancing-Master* (12th edn; J. Heptinstall, 1703), 261 (Public Domain, *IMSLP*)

Example 5 - 'Childgrove' as realised by Bellowhead

Example 6 - Transcription of 'Mr. Isaac's Maggot' from *The English Acoustic Collective* recording, Ghost (2004).

Much of folk ornamentation uses the same grace notes as classical ornaments but is very distinct in execution. Most notably, classical players tend to anticipate the beat with their ornaments whereas folk players try to ornament *on* the beat. This also

means that folk ornaments are often executed quicker than their classical counterparts so as to maintain a steady, danceable pulse.

The ‘yup’ – It is a feature of folk music that the technical quirks of the dominant instrument in any particular tradition will often hold stylistic sway over the instruments. For example, the need to use fingered ornaments to distinguish between repeated notes when playing the Highland bagpipes leads naturally to the ‘cran’ ornament (where a low note is rhythmically separated by a series of higher grace notes). It is, however, an entirely unnatural way to separate notes on a fiddle, but the dominance of the pipes within that tradition has led to the development of an imitative fingered fiddle ornament style. Similarly, the characteristic use of rolls as a rhythmical device in Irish piping ornamentation has been adopted by fiddles, flutes, whistles, and accordions in Ireland despite those instruments having far more natural rhythmic mechanisms at their disposal.

In English folk music the dominant instruments, since their invention in the nineteenth century, has been the concertina and melodeon. One of the unusual quirks of these small, light free reed instruments is they naturally lend themselves to the ‘yup,’ that is to say a quick crescendo on a note (creating by a swell in bellows pressure) terminating in a sudden staccato stop (with the release of the fingers.) This yup will often anticipate the beat in its swell, but land solidly on the beat with the stop. This is an extremely useful stylistic feature when trying to make music feel ‘danceable,’ and is particularly utilised when accompanying Cotswold Morris dance, in which the athletic jumping figures are often mimicked musically by this ‘yup’ technique. As it anticipates the beat this also ties into the swing/swagger stylistic elements discussed above.

Using the ‘yup’ is another way in which the folk player will bring these archaic melodies into the

stylistic milieu of contemporary folk, for example when playing ‘Argiers’, John Spiers will often play something akin to the transcription in example 7 for the B music.

Aggression is another variable in folk music that is prized in different measure depending on the regional style. English folk styles tend to fall into the pro-aggression category, as best typified by Eliza Carthy who tackled the Playford tune ‘Stingo’ on her ground-breaking, Mercury-nominated 1998 album *Red Rice* and, later on, with the brass-infused Wayward Band. The fiddle is particularly well suited to an expression of aggression as extreme bow pressure leads to a grungy effect not unlike electric guitar distortion. This is particularly effective when combined with heavy tension double-stopping of open strings.

Tonality, or lack thereof, is one of the interesting features of Playford’s manuscripts, as there is a lack of harmonic information. The tunes are presented monophonically without any indication of where the tonal centre should lie (which would otherwise be made clear through the inclusion of a continuo line). In many tunes the tonality is implicit, but in others it is at the discretion of the player (or the arranger) to make those choices.

A good example of this is the tune ‘Kettledrum’ (example 8). This 1651 edition score is written in what modern readers would interpret as octave bass clef (G1). The band ‘1651’—Andy Cutting (Melodeon), Mark Emmerson (Fiddle, Piano) Tim Harries (Double Bass)—chose to interpret this tune as a driving minor-key melody (example 9 here transposed to D minor) starting on the 2nd note of the scale.

The image shows a musical score for a melody in 4/4 time, written on a single staff. The key signature has one sharp (F#). The melody consists of several measures, each containing a 'yup' ornament. The ornaments are indicated by downward-pointing arrows above the notes. The dynamic markings are *mf*, *p* < *f*, *mf*, *p* < *f*, *mf*, *p* < *f*, *mf*, *p* < *f*, *mf*. The notation includes slurs, accents, and staccato markings.

Example 7 - The ‘yup’, as might be played by John Spiers in ‘Argiers’

Kettle Drum

A round Dance for eight

Example 8 – ‘Kettledrum’, printed in J. Playford, *The English Dancing Master* (London: T. Harper, 1651), 89 (Public Domain, IMSLP)

Example 9 - 'Kettledrum' as realised by 1651, harmonised into D minor, written in treble clef (G2).

There is something fundamentally awkward about this harmonic approach - starting on the 2nd note of the scale is discombobulating and concluding the B section with two bars of the tonic chord is, well, weird. The single G# effectively becomes a ‘blue’ note when used above a Dm harmonisation - not at all in keeping with standard folk sensibilities let alone its seventeenth-century origins. And yet this approach is by far the most common in folk pub sessions. I have written Am in bar one, but in fact it often feels more like a second inversion Dm chord in the ‘1651’s version, again adding to a sense of tension and dissonance by, in effect, beginning the tune with a Dmsus2 chord over an A bass. This awkwardness is actually very appealing to the folkly mindset – in its weirdness, in the potential for dissonance, folkies find excitement and musical drama.

A rarer, and yet more harmonically conventional approach is that of Oxfordshire folk band, Magpie

Lane, who interpret the same melody as being in the major scale (example 10).

This now becomes a gentle, plaintive melody harmonised very simply and consonantly with the tonic, subdominant and dominant alone. There is something inherently contemporary, almost ‘pop’ about this harmonisation, something beguilingly modern in having both sections end on the dominant chord.

In order to make it work more naturally Magpie Lane have done away with the troublesome G# at the end of bar seven. To the folk mind this sort of alteration is simply part of the evolution of the tune and is entirely in keeping with how the tune *might* have evolved had it survived in the repertoire of, say, a village morris side, accidentals being more or less obliterated by the invention and subsequent preponderance of the diatonic melodeon in the nineteenth century.

The Night-Peece Longways for six

Example 13 - 'The Night Piece' as printed in Playford, *The English Dancing Master* (London: T. Harper, 1651), 3 (Public Domain, IMSLP)

Example 14 - 'The Night Piece' as printed in Playford, *The English Dancing Master* (2nd edn; London: 1652), 69 (Public Domain, IMSLP)

If, as seems possible, Playford was correcting transcription mistakes made in the first edition, it leads to the intriguing possibility that some tunes have prospered as session-friendly folk tunes *because* Playford mistakenly omitted key signatures in the original edition. Whether or not that is the case, it is still clear that the harmonic ambiguity of the Playford melodies—both through the lack of notated harmony and through their melodic simplicity—is of great appeal to the folk mindset, allowing different players to come up with radically different versions of ostensibly the same melody.

Harmony — Even where the tonal centre of the melodies is fixed and not in dispute, the whole feel of any given tune is open to huge variations through harmonisation. Whereas the trained early musician will be drawn to harmonisations that reflect practises as determined by treatises, folk players are more likely to actively avoid ‘conventional’ chord changes and to seek out more modern sounding cadences.

Nineteenth century ‘free-reed’ instruments such as piano accordion, diatonic melodeon and the various types of concertina are central to the English folk sound, and have a huge impact upon the harmonic conventions of the scene. An extremely common harmonic trope since the 1990s is to hold a low tonic note as a bass drone and play the tonic, sub-dominant and dominant triads above to form a warm but slightly suspended accompaniment. This is particularly favoured by

piano-accordion players as the left hand ‘stradella’ system makes this the simplest and yet most pleasing (to modern folk ears at any rate) method of harmonising a diatonic major tune.

The duo Belshazzars Feast consisted of fiddle and oboe player extraordinaire Paul Sartin (who sadly passed away in 2022, aged 51) and piano accordion maestro Paul Hutchinson. Paul Hutchinson uses this I/IV/V over a tonic drone figure extensively (alongside far more complex left hand accordion work) and their 2001 album of Playford Tunes *John Playford’s Secret Ball* is no exception, such as ‘The Garland’ (‘The Garter’ in Playford), example 15. Leveret also uses this extensively on Andy Cutting’s melodeon and/or Rob Harbron’s concertina, for example in ‘Mr Lane’s Minuet’.

This approach of diatonic chord-changes played over a drone is also common in guitar accompaniment. Kevin Lees and Sebastian Bloch are a folk duo based in Newcastle Upon Tyne. In an excellent A major arrangement of Grimstock recently posted on their website, Bloch (guitar) takes this approach using open guitar tuning, and the suspension-rich harmony is emphasised by Lees also tuning his fiddle to open A (AEAE) and so is able to add tonic chord harmonisation on double-stopped fiddle when guitar is playing any of the six diatonic major/minor chords underneath.

Improvisation and variation are a huge part of English tune playing, even more so than in the

more established Scottish/Irish/Swedish folk playing traditions. In the pub session context improvisation is normally in the form of short phrases that either harmonise with, counterpoint to, or create dynamic tension with the primary melody being played collectively. The spaciousness of Playford tunes lend themselves well to this approach, particularly inviting contrapuntal extemporisation, as illustrated by the Leveret and English Acoustic Collective examples above.

More free-form improvisation (akin to jazz soloing) is very rare in folk tune playing contexts, but not unheard of. It's interesting that two of the few bands from the folk scene who are specifically interested in using more free-form improvisation, were/are also specifically focused on the Playford repertoire: 'The Playford Liberation Front' and '1651'.

The Playford Liberation Front (who continue to perform) utilise a reasonably conventional folk-band line up (accordion, fiddle, bass guitar, pipes) but unusually add a soloistic, improvisatory clarinet line over the top, reminiscent of Klezmer.

Even more unusually the band 1651 built whole pieces around the stating of a Playford melody, followed by an extended improvised section played over a drone or over the chord-changes established during the opening section.

Group arrangement approaches

The approach to ensemble arrangement within the folk scene is different to early music methods. There is a tendency in the folk scene to try to use modern instruments, or at least modern versions of old instruments. So, for example, ninety percent of guitars employed in the folk scene are steel-strung acoustics rather than gut/nylon strung. With Victorian instruments such as melodeons and accordions, these now tend to be 'dry tuned' to sound more contemporary than heavy 'beating' of Jimmy Shand-style tunings that were popular in the first half of the twentieth century. Oboes and clarinets are not exactly common in the English folk scene, but they are far more common than

period wind instruments (shawms, crumhorns etc.) Period string instruments such as viols and lutes are hardly ever used and even recorders are generally eschewed in favour of the Victorian-era tin whistle. One area of instrumental crossover is with bagpipes and hurdy gurdies. Unlike in Ireland, the English bagpipe did not evolve into a sophisticated eighteenth century instrument, so when bagpipes are used they tend to be fairly similar in timbre to period instruments (John Swayne's 'English Border Pipes' being the most common on the English folk scene) and hurdy gurdies are (as far as I'm aware) built and set up the same whether played for early or folk music (though the stylistic approach, particularly in the syncopated use of the rhythmical 'trompette' is quite distinct.) Hurdy gurdies and bagpipes are more associated with the strong French/Euro Folk music scene (often socially linked to, but distinct from, the English Folk scene), the band 'Blowzabella' (named after the Playford tune) being the key exponents in England.

Conventional drum kits are fairly common in the English scene (on the concert performance end of things rather than the session scene) and have often been used with Playford tunes. The classic folk-rock sound typified by drummer Dave Mattacks maps on to Playford's 'Picking of Sticks' without difficulty (example 16).

An interest in the use of brass instruments has been a small but significant element of the English folk scene since the 1970s, most notably in that decade in the form of Brass Monkey, who fused a marching brass-band feel with melodeon-led English repertoire. Example 17 includes the *Dancing Master* tune 'Dr Fauster's Tumblers'.

Other English folk bands have experimented with pop-style brass sections, perhaps most recognisably with my own band Bellowhead, who have tackled several Playford tunes including 'Childgrove' (mentioned above), 'Argiers' and 'Parson's Farewell' (see example 18).

Example 15 - 'The Garland', as played by Belshazzar's Feast. *John Playford's Secret Ball*. 2018.

Example 16 - 'Picking of Sticks' with added Drum Kit

This 'festival band brass' approach was also employed to great effect by Eliza Carthy and The Wayward Band in their version of the Playford tune *Stingo*. Playford melodies in their original form tend to have simple, clean melodic lines compared to more modern folk tunes. This melodic clarity lends itself to contrapuntal brass stabs as a) there is space for them and b) the melodies themselves are more likely to suggest suitable brass lines that echo the main melody.

As has been mentioned, the folk scene tends to be drawn to modern instrumentation and eschew period instruments. It is not wholly surprising therefore that many folk performers over the years have been drawn to digital music making, or EDM (Electronic Dance Music.) Notable exponents of this in the Scottish and Irish scenes include Martyn

Bennet and The Afro Celt Sound System. In general, English folk tunes have not proved quite as amenable to digital arrangement (probably because of the need to maintain swing - see above) but several performers have experimented with it, for example Eliza Carthy with her 1998 track *Red Rice*.

Again, the melodic simplicity of Playford tunes lends itself more to a digital approach than heavily swung Morris tunes or complex country dance tunes, but it is still quite surprising to discover that no less than three artists (James Bell, Ben & Sel, and Chris Green) have experimented with fully digital arrangements of Playford tunes. In this extreme, digital-only format there is so little of the stylistic features of the folk scene (as detailed above) remaining that objectively they have no

more, or less, to do with the folk scene than they do with early music practices. But the fact that these artists all come from/interface with the folk scene rather than the early music scene is illustrative of their being part of a continuum of experimental folk-scene approaches to Playford, albeit on the extreme wing.

Folk sessions - conventions and transpositions

Any musician, from whatever musical background, turning up to a pub folk session in England who has memorised some Playford tunes is likely to find that many of the other players in the room will know them and happily join in. However, it's worth noting that folk sessions (whilst in many ways inclusive and welcoming) do have a whole series of unspoken rules that it is easy for the newcomer to miss or be flummoxed by. One such rule is that sheet music is never used - if you haven't memorised it, don't play it. Tunes tend to be played in sets of three, often with each tune being played three times round. A feature of folk sessions that is second nature to regular attendees is that tunes tend to only be played in certain keys. There is some leeway with this but in general keys that can readily be played on a D major tin whistle are favoured: D & G major (A at a push), E and A minor(s), B aeolian, D dorian at a push. Therefore, it is very likely that any Playford tunes that are played will not be played in the key in which they have been published. A musical newcomer to folk sessions turning up with a repertoire of Playford tunes might therefore be well advised to learn them in one of these keys in preference to the written key.

Conclusions – There are a huge number of recorded versions of Playford melodies within the English folk scene and the repertoire continues to maintain a strong presence in English folk pub sessions. Why do so many folk musicians choose to play Playford? There are many eighteenth- and nineteenth-century manuscripts that contain tunes that are more of a piece with contemporary folk tune repertoire: folk tune players may dip into this or that collection to find tunes, but no single manuscript comes even close to Playford in terms

of ubiquity within the folk scene. The Playford repertoire is at the same time outlier and core repertoire.

As mentioned above, a paradox of the unspoken philosophy of the English Folk Scene is that it performs antiquated material whilst being highly preoccupied with its contemporary relevance. Music, for the folk musician, is about evolution not antiquity, about furthering 'the tradition' rather than recreating the past. The 'composed' (whether from the seventeenth or the twenty-first century) is often seen as of less weight than material which has been passed down through a number of generations. The guiding philosophy behind these underpinning value judgements is in part Darwinian, but more importantly it is collectivist - the sense that material with no single author is in some way owned by everyone. This has even led to a culture of sublimated authorship – of folk musicians downplaying their own creative input (or in extreme cases completely inventing a fake traditional source) in order for their composed or semi-composed material to be accepted as legitimately 'traditional' by the folk scene at large.

Playford's place within this is complex. On the one hand there is something a little too 'composed' about many of the tunes for conventional folk taste, and some of the more baroque cadences are tolerated rather than enjoyed by the folk player. And yet the Playford repertoire has so much to offer the folk player that is often not present in more modern repertoire. The melodic simplicity affords the player huge scope in terms of individual interpretation and musical reinvention. The lack of a defined stylistic framework means each player can bring to bear their own musical proclivities. Playford melodies are, comparatively speaking, a blank canvas upon which the folk-player can paint their own stylistic, harmonic, ornamental, genre-bending conceptions of contemporary folk 'Englishness' and, despite (or, perhaps, *because of*) being further removed chronologically than any other material played, it is often in the Playford repertoire that English folk players find the apotheosis of their own personal style. There is a

sense in which, to the folk musician's mind, the Playford tunes represent pre-evolved folk tunes, so the modern player feels empowered to mimic the evolutionary process of three hundred and fifty years of aural transmission through their own musical mediation.

In short folk players keep coming back to Playford because these seventeenth-century tunes are useful in the folk player's mission to sound individual, contemporary, edgy, and experimental whilst staying rooted within established traditions and grounded in a sense of historical legitimacy. And, of course, because they are great tunes to play.

Jon Boden

Musical score for Example 17, 'Doctor Fauster's Tumblers'. The score is in 2/4 time with a tempo marking of quarter note = 78. It features two staves: Trumpet / concertina (treble clef, key signature of one sharp) and Trombone (bass clef, key signature of one sharp). The music consists of a series of rhythmic patterns and melodic lines.

Example 17 – 'Doctor Fauster's Tumblers' as played by Brass Monkey. 'Doctor Fauster's Tumblers/The Night of Trafalgar/Prince William'. *The Complete Brass Monkey*. 1983.

Musical score for Example 18, 'Parson's Farewell'. The score is in 2/4 time and features six staves: Melody (treble clef, key signature of one flat), Soprano Saxophone (treble clef, key signature of one flat), Trumpet in Bb (treble clef, key signature of two flats), Trombone (bass clef, key signature of two flats), Sousaphone in Bb (bass clef, key signature of two flats), and Drum Set (percussion clef). The score includes dynamic markings such as *f* and *mf*, and various rhythmic notations.

Example 18 - 'Parson's Farewell' as played by Bellowhead. Reassembled. 2021.

Select Discography

Band/Artist(s)	Track	Album (and Link)	Date
Albion Dance Band	Picking of Sticks / The Old Mole	The Prospect Before Us	1977
Bellowhead	Parson's farewell	Reassembled	2021
Belshazzar's Feast	All tracks Playford	John Playford's Secret Ball	2018
Ben and Sel	The Shepherd and Shepherdess	Traditional Tunes in a New Style	2023
Blackbeards Tea Party	Hummeabar (Kettledrum)	Heaven's to Betsy	2009
Brass Monkey	Doctor Fauster's Tumblers / The Night of Trafalgar / Prince William	The Complete Brass Monkey	1983
Chris Green	All tracks Playford	Switched on Playford	2018
Eliza Carthy	Stingo	Red Rice	1998
English Acoustic Collective	Hare's Maggot / Mr Isaac's Maggot	Ghosts	2004
James Bell	The Shepherd and Shepherdess	Unreleased track	2011
John Kirkpatrick	Once I Loved a Maiden Fair / The Hole in the Wall / Amaryllis	One Man and His Box	1999
Jumpleads	Hunt The Squirrel, La Montarde	The Stag Must Die	1982
Kevin Lees & Sebastian Bloch	Grimstock	The Good Tune	2024
Leveret	Mr Lane's Minuet	Forms	2023
Playford Liberation Front	Trip To Kilburn (Black and Grey)	Three Track Demo	2016
Spiers & Boden	Jack Robinson / Argiers / Old Tom of Oxford	Bellow	2004

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Jestbooks and Drinking Songs William Byrd and Popular Culture

Katherine Butler

In John Hilton's *Catch that Catch Can* printed by John Playford in 1652, an unexpected name appears next to the drinking song 'Come Drink to Me / I Have Loved the Jolly Tankard': 'Mr William Bird.'¹ Byrd's name was spuriously attached to many catches in the mid- to late-eighteenth century, including most famously, *Non nobis Domine*;² however this appearance in Playford's collection was less than 30-years after Byrd's death. Nor was it a Latin canon or a country catch (like the equally spurious 'Hey Ho! to the Greenwood'), but rather a drinking song.

Hilton's *Catch that Catch Can* was not the first appearance of 'Come Drink to Me / I Have Loved the Jolly Tankard', which had been previously printed anonymously by Thomas Ravenscroft in 1609 and a year earlier by John Playford in 1651.³ All Ravenscroft's rounds and catches had been printed without attribution. However, the majority of Latin canons in Ravenscroft's print have now been identified as from a continental theory treatise, and it is by no means impossible that some others were by well-known composers of the day.⁴ At this point in its history, the catch was not a genre to associate one's name with (even Ravenscroft kept his identity hidden in his earliest publications).

'Come Drink to Me / I Have Loved the Jolly Tankard' is at the more complex end of the catch spectrum. The catch is built on a scalar hexachordal ground (sung to 'Come Drink to Me'), around which lengthy phrases are woven and out of which

finally emerges a faster, triple time melody that seems likely to be a popular drinking song of the day. Nevertheless, the catch has been rejected from the Byrd canon and was criticised by Philip Brett for being 'rhythmically square' and 'harmonically awkward' with its parallel octaves.⁵

In the 1652 publication, Byrd's name is only given in the table of contents but is not printed next to the notated song. This is unusual, as the reverse is usually true in this collection.⁶ This oddity perhaps suggests that the name was initially a last-minute addition in 1652 and that either Playford or Hilton became aware of the attribution late in the production process. Yet the appearance of Byrd's name against this catch is also not a one-off; rather it was continuously associated with Byrd in Playford's catchbooks. Indeed, in all subsequent editions Byrd's name follows the norm and appears above the notated song rather than in the contents, thereby becoming even more closely associated with the song as singers would have seen it if performing the catch from notation.⁷ It is highly likely, therefore, that seventeenth-century catch singers would have believed 'Come Drink to Me / I Have Loved the Jolly Tankard' to be by William Byrd.

My aim here, though, is not to resituate this catch in the Byrd canon. Attributions in catchbooks are often unreliable (though it is worth noting that this occurrence is not symptomatic of any wider trend of associating older anonymous catches to Byrd or

¹ John Hilton, ed, *Catch that Catch Can, or A Choice Collection of Catches, Rounds and Canons for 3 or 4 Voyces* (London, 1652), Table of Contents and 70.

² See Philip Brett, 'Did Byrd Write "Non Nobis, Domine"?' *The Musical Times*, 113 (1972), 855–7; more recently on possible attributions for *Non nobis Domine* see David Humphreys, 'Wilder's Hand?', *The Musical Times*, 144 (2003), 4. Byrd's earliest biographers did accept these pieces in the Byrd canon, as in Edmund Fellowes, *William Byrd*, 2nd edn (London: Oxford University Press, 1948), 173–82.

³ Thomas Ravenscroft, *Pammelia, Musicks Miscellanie, or Mixed Varietie of Pleasant Roundelays, and Delightfull Catches of 3.4.5.6.7.8.9.10. Parts in One* (London, 1609), p.31 (No. 68); John Playford, ed., *Musick and Mirth, Presented in a Choice Collection of Rounds or Catches for Three Voyces* (London, 1651), 5.

⁴ John Milsom, 'About a Round', *Music of the Josquin Era* (forthcoming).

⁵ Brett, 'Did Byrd Write "Non Nobis, Domine"?' 856.

⁶ Aside from the numerous *Gloria Patri* settings that are distinguished by their composer, the only secular song whose composer is named in the table of contents is *Now that the Spring* by John Hilton himself, which also appears without attribution on p.1 of the collection.

⁷ In the John Hilton and John Playford, ed., *Catch that Catch Can, or A Choice Collection of Catches, Rounds and Canons: Being Three or Foure Parts in One* (London, 1658), 66; *Catch that Catch Can Or A New Collection of Catches, Rounds and Canons: Being Three or Four Parts in One* (London, 1663), 66; John Playford, ed., *Catch that Catch Can or The Musical Companion* (London, 1667), 26; and in John Playford, ed., *The Musical Companion in Two Books The First Containing Catches and Rounds for Three Voyces* (London, 1672/3), 20.

other composers of his generation in Playford's collections). I am more interested in the fact that it was presumably plausible for seventeenth-century musicians—including a Cambridge-trained and London-based church musician such as John Hilton—to associate a drinking song catch with Byrd. This offers a quite different perspective on Byrd's image in the immediate generation that succeeded him and gives us pause to reconsider the nuances of his posthumous reputation, especially as it might have been viewed by those more removed from the composer's immediate circle and shaped by those more ubiquitous genres that traversed orality and print.

When discussing Byrd's reputation among his contemporaries or immediately succeeding generations, the sources that have tended to be cited by scholars are those that emphasise Byrd's high esteem and serious nature. For example, colleagues in the Chapel Royal such as Thomas Morley described Byrd as 'neuer without reuerence to be named of the musicians', while in his commonplace book John Baldwin labelled him, 'famus man of skill: and iudgement greate profounde'.⁸ In a popular conduct book of the day for gentlemen, Henry Peacham described Byrd as 'being of himselfe naturally disposed to Grauitie and Pietie, his veine is not so much for light Madrigals or Canzonets'.⁹ This image of the serious Byrd who troubled himself little with 'light' or 'foreign' genres such as the madrigal has endured in Byrd scholarship.¹⁰ Byrd's first biographer, Edmund Fellowes took his lead from Peacham, stating that 'rightly recognised that... this special excellence was due to his natural disposition to "Gravitie and Pietie"'.¹¹ Elsewhere, Fellowes

described Byrd as a man who 'commanded affection and respect. And he was a man of deep and sincere religious conviction'.¹² While more recent biographers tend to be more cautious in offering such explicit character judgements, such an image of Byrd is still current in the *Grove Music* article begun by Joseph Kerman and updated by Kerry McCarthy when it states: 'Decorum, solidity and a certain reticence of expression were qualities that were prized in his formative years, qualities that came to him naturally'.¹³ Indeed, the *Grove Music* article does not even mention the catches and canons in the list of spurious works, so keen is current scholarship to dissociate such frivolities from Byrd.

However, these lofty, laudatory statements by gentlemen and prominent colleagues were not the only sources through which Byrd's reputation was formed and disseminated. As Mike Smith has noted, several of Byrd songs and instrumental variations seem to reveal a liking for bawdy ballad tunes and lyrics that indicates a neglected lighter side to Byrd's creativity and character.¹⁴ Moreover Byrd makes several appearances in one of the most widespread and popular genres of print during his lifetime: the jestbook. Jestbooks were collections of merry tales, jokes, and witty repartees designed to produce laughter. Although the culture of jesting was oral in nature, jestbooks could take a wide variety of forms including individual detached jests, short comic stories, or longer pseudo-biographical narratives of the escapades of a central character.¹⁵ Almost all jestbooks were anonymous, but many associated themselves with real but now-dead comic figures such as John Scoggin and Richard Tarlton, or else with figures of popular legend such

⁸ Thomas Morley, *A Plaine and Easie Introduction to Practicall Musicke* (London, 1597), 115; British Library, R.M.24.d.2 'Baldwin Commonplace Book', final pages.

⁹ Henry Peacham, *The Compleat Gentleman Fashioning him Absolute in the Most Necessary & Commendable Qualities Concerning Minde or Bodie that may be Required in a Noble Gentleman* (London, 1622), 100.

¹⁰ On the notion of 'light' music in early modern times and in contemporary scholarship see Katie Bank, *Knowledge Building in Early Modern English Music* (Abingdon, 2021), chap. 1.

¹¹ Fellowes, *William Byrd*, 241.

¹² *Ibid.*

¹³ Joseph Kerman and Kerry McCarthy, 'Byrd, William', *Grove Music Online* (2001) <<https://doi.org/10.1093/gmo/9781561592630.article.04487>>.

¹⁴ Mike Smith, 'Bawdry, Balladry, Byrd', *Annual Byrd Newsletter* 10 (2004), 16–19. Smith also notes previous passing comments on Byrd's engagement with such themes by John Milsom, Oliver Neighbour and Laurence Dreyfus.

¹⁵ This tripartite definition of types of jestbooks originates in E. Schulz, *Die englischen Schwankbücher bis herab zu Dobson's Drie Bobs, Palaestra* 117 (Berlin, 1912), but still informs modern critical approaches to the genre: Ian Munro and Anne Lake Prescott, 'Jest Books' *The Oxford Handbook of English Prose 1500-1640*, ed. Andrew Hadfield, (Oxford, 2013), 343–59 (at 344); F. P. Wilson, 'The English Jestbooks of the Sixteenth and Early Seventeenth Centuries', *Huntington Library Quarterly* 2 (1939), 121–58 (at 122).

as George a Green, Long Meg, and Oliver Smug.¹⁶ Within these books, the same jests were often recycled and retold from collection to collection.¹⁷ The chapbook format of many jestbooks give them the appearance of popular literature: cheaply printed, small pamphlets in blackletter type, set in common, everyday contexts and addressing coarse topics.¹⁸ However, jests had classical pedigree having been praised by ancient authors such as Cicero and Quintilian, and humanistic discourse promoted the revival of classical wit and the benefits of jesting for health, conviviality, rhetoric, and political ambition.¹⁹ Indeed jestbooks often anticipated a broad and multifarious audience. *The Booke of Bulls* (1636) has prefaces ‘to the blinde reader’, and ‘to the discerning reader’ while John Taylor’s *Wit and Mirth* (1628) describes its content as originating in taverns, alehouses, tobacco shops, highways, water-passages, but ‘apothegmatically bundled vp’, referring to the verse tags that he adds to draw out their potential moral message or meaning.²⁰ Jestbooks evoked the broad spectrum of potential readers, contexts, and responses to their contents.

Byrd makes two jestbook appearances: the first in *Dobsons Drie Bobbes Sonne and Heire to Skoggin* (London, 1607) and the second in *Tarltons Iests Drawne into these Three Parts* (London, 1613, but circulating at least in partial form by 1590s).²¹ I will also briefly discuss a possible third jestbook appearance that has been connected with Byrd in *The Booke of Bulls, Baited with Two Centuries of Bold Jestes* (London, 1636), though in this case I will argue that the ‘Byrd’ in question is not the composer. This article will review Byrd’s jestbook appearances and

their potential impact on Byrd’s image in the eyes of his near contemporaries, reflecting on how this might lead us to adjust aspects of our own view of the composer today.

Although the date at which the third part of *Tarltons Iests* initially appeared is uncertain, ‘Tarlton’s Wit between a Bird and a Woodcocke’ is likely to have been Byrd’s most well-known jestbook appearance.²² Richard Tarleton was a comic actor in the Queen’s Men and the Queen’s favourite jester.²³ After his death in 1588, Tarleton’s name was attached to several jestbooks including *Tarltons Iests*.²⁴ This book is a loose collection of jests unified only by association with the hero Tarleton and grouped into three categories: court, city, and country. As was common for the genre, many of *Tarltons Iests* recycle older, traditional jests;²⁵ however, the jest in which William Byrd appears seems to be new as it depends specifically on his name and that of the lesser-known Tudor composer, Clement Woodcock.

The Byrd-related jest opens ‘*Tarltons prettie Countrie Iests*’, by which is meant jests that take place out of London, rather than necessarily in a rural location. The Byrd jest is short enough to cite in full:

In the City of Gloucester, Master Bird of the Chappell met with Tarlton, who joyfull to regreet other, went to visit his friends: amongst the rest, M. Bird of the Queens Chappell visited Master Woodcock of the Colledge, where méeting, many friendly speeches past, amongst which, M. Woodcocke challenged M. Bird of kin:

¹⁶ Munro and Prescott, ‘Jest Books’, 352–7; Wilson, ‘English Jestbooks’, 133–8; Adam Smyth, ‘“Divines into Dry Vines”: Forms of Jestings in Renaissance England’, in *Formal Matters: Reading the Materials of English Renaissance Literature*, ed. A. K. Eutermann and A. Kisey (Manchester, 2013), 55–76 (at 59–60).

¹⁷ Wilson, ‘English Jestbooks’, 126; Smyth, ‘Divines into Dry Vines’, 59; Tim Somers, ‘Jesting Culture and Religious Politics in Seventeenth-Century England’, *Historical Research*, 95 (2022), 19–44 (21–22).

¹⁸ Munro and Prescott, ‘Jest Books’, 354; Somers, ‘Jesting Culture’, 20–21; Smyth, ‘Divines into Dry Vines’, 65.

¹⁹ Munro and Prescott, ‘Jest Books’, 345–51; Smyth, ‘Divines into Dry Vines’, 63–5.

²⁰ John Taylor, *Wit and Mirth Chargeably Collected out of Tauernes, Ordinaries, Innes, Bowling Greenes, and Allyes, Alehouses, Tobacco Shops, Highwaies, and Water-Passages: Made Vp, and Fashioned into Clinches, Bulls, Quirkes, Yerkes, Quips, and Ierkes: Apothegmatically Bundled Vp and Garbled at the Request of Old Iohn Garrets Ghost* (London, 1628); A.S. Gent, *The Booke of Bulls Baited with Two Centuries of Bold Jestes, and Nimble-Lies, Or a Combat betweene Sense and Non-sense, being at Strike who Shall Infuse Most Myrth into the Gentle-Reader* (London, 1636), prefatory materials.

²¹ The second part of *Tarltons Iests* was registered in 1600: <<https://stationersregister.online/entry/SRO4330>>. In 1609, *Tarltons Iests* were reassigned to John Budge: <<https://stationersregister.online/entry/SRO5572>>.

²² *Tarltons Iests Drawne into These Three Parts* (London, 1613), sig.[C4]r.

²³ For more detail see Katherine Duncan-Jones, ‘The Life, Death and Afterlife of Richard Tarlton’, *The Review of English Studies* New. Ser 65 (2014), 18–32.

²⁴ Munro and Prescott, ‘Jest Books’, 356–7.

²⁵ P. M. Zall, *A Nest of Ninnies and Other English Jestbooks of the Seventeenth Century* (Lincoln, NE, 1970), 91.

who mused that he was of his affinity and he never knew it: yes says M. Woodcocke, every Woodcocke is a Bird, therefore it must needs be so. Lord, Sir, says Tarlton, you are wide, for though every Woodcocke be a Bird, yet every Bird is not a Woodcocke. So M. Woodcocke like a Woodcocke bit his lip, and mum bugged was silent.²⁶

Despite the verisimilitude given by details of the people and places, this jest should not be read literally as an anecdotal account of an actual meeting. Nevertheless, the people and places would presumably have been plausible to contemporary readers. Gloucester might seem an odd place to situate Byrd, but the city was only a few miles from the manor of Longney, which he was granted by the Queen in 1577, and which was one of the subjects of his many legal issues.²⁷ Clement Woodcock (c.1540–90) was a contemporary of Byrd's with five surviving consort pieces (including two In Nomines and two arrangements of popular tunes). He was a Lay Clerk at King's College, a singer at Canterbury Cathedral until 1570, and then Organist and Master of the Choristers at Chichester Cathedral, but has no known connection to Gloucester.²⁸

There are two key elements to the jest. The first is a pun on the composers' ornithological names. The woodcock is a woodland wading bird, which was known in Tudor times for being dull and particularly easy to snare. As such, 'woodcock' was also a name often applied to a gullible or foolish person, a characterisation that the composer lives up to in this jest.²⁹ The second element to the jest is that of an attempt at wit that backfires on the instigator to the amusement of others. Tarlton's rejoinder plays on the relative status of the composers, and the presumptuousness of Woodcock in claiming affinity with a musician of Byrd's status. The clear message is that Byrd is a different class of musician, and Woodcock is a fool to be so unaware of his place in the pecking order.

The jest both expects the audience to know who Byrd is and further enhances Byrd's status through his endorsement by such a famous and popular figure as Tarleton. Admiration for Tarleton spanned the spectrum of Tudor society from the Queen and court to the London theatregoer. Tarleton's endorsement was all the more realistic as his regular appearances at court meant that he would likely have known of Byrd's status as a favoured musician of the Queen (indeed he may even have met Byrd on one of these court occasions). *Tarltons Iests* was a chapbook of only 24 folios printed in blackletter type, the same as used for broadside ballads and the first script one would be taught to read.³⁰ Such jestbooks were designed to appeal and be accessible to a broad readership, so the effect of this jest would have been to similarly popularise Byrd's status beyond the courtly and aristocratic audiences who purchased his music publications or had ready access to hearing his music performed. Moreover, with repeated editions in 1620, 1630, and 1638, *Tarltons Iests* continued to shape Byrd's posthumous identity too.

Byrd's other jestbook appearance came in *Dobsons Drie Bobbes* (1607). This book was a jest biofiction that told the story of the life of George Dobson, a choirboy at Durham Cathedral School, and later scholar at Christ's College, Cambridge. At the start of the story Dobson is adopted by his uncle. Initially mocked and bullied by his classmates for his country manner, Dobson eventually decides to turn troublemaker and get his revenge. 'Dry bobs' are pranks and escapades, and those Dobson plays on his classmates include locking them in cupboards, stealing from them, and tricking them into sitting on hot stones that burn through the seat of their trousers.

Dobsons Drie Bobbes has such a high degree of verisimilitude in the places, customs, legal/financial technicalities, and detailed descriptions of material objects which it contains that it has been regarded

²⁶ *Tarltons Iests*, sig.[C4]r.

²⁷ John Harley, *The World of William Byrd: Musicians, Merchants and Magnates* (Burlington, VT, 2010), 219.

²⁸ Warwick Edwards, 'Woodcock, Clement', *Grove Music Online* (2001) <<https://doi.org/10.1093/gmo/9781561592630.article.30547>>.

²⁹ *Oxford English Dictionary*, 'woodcock (n.)' (2023) <<https://doi.org/10.1093/OED/8470115952>>.

³⁰ Keith Thomas, 'The Meaning of Literacy in Early Modern England,' in *The Written Word: Literacy in Transition*, ed. Gerd Baumann (Oxford, 1986), 97–131 (at 99).

by literary scholars as a work of historical fiction.³¹ Although published in 1607 and assumed to be written around the same time, the characters are identifiable figures who were living and working in Durham during the 1560s, including the protagonist George Dobson (a known choirboy), his uncle Sir Thomas Pentley (a canon at the cathedral), fellow chorister Raikebaines, and John Bromley, master of the choir school and organist. Moreover, the places featured are similarly realistic, including the local churches and layout of Durham cathedral precinct, and the text is full of specific details about customs, rituals, objects, and legal, financial, or ecclesiastical technicalities.³²

The reference to Byrd is another of these realistic details which appears in Dobson's last school prank: 'How Dobson devised a holiday and endangered his fellows a whipping'.³³ The somewhat convoluted escapade takes place around Midsummer. The choristers have finished morning prayers at the cathedral and are on their way to school. Dobson uses the chance closure of the Tailor's shop to convince his peers that there is in fact no school because it is a feast day and a holiday. Dobson encourages them to go instead to the Moorhouse (presumably an alehouse or tavern) where he tells them that he has laid on breakfast and a shooting match.³⁴ Dobson promises to go to the schoolhouse to get permission from the schoolmaster for them to observe the holiday.

Dobson does go to the schoolhouse; however, when the schoolmaster, Master Bromeley, arrives, Dobson plays the innocent and claims that his classmates are the ones suggesting the holiday and that he dared not go with them to shoot because he could not think what holiday it could be, and nor could he persuade his peers to wait until Master Bromeley arrived. Bromeley checks that there is no

holiday and then sends Dobson to command his peers to come back to school. Dobson therefore returns to his peers but spins them the story that 'diuers Gentlemen of good sort' have arrived from London on their way to Berwick.³⁵ The gentlemen, he claims, have sought out Master Bromeley wanting to see the school and its scholars, and so the Master has sent Dobson to ask them to come to school, despite it being a holiday.

Crucially for our interest in the story, Dobson states that the gentlemen from London have requested a song 'and haue brought themselues diuersitie of descant, lately set forth by Maister *Bird Doctor of our Arte*'.³⁶ Believing Dobson's tale, the pupils head back to the school hoping to be rewarded by the gentlemen for their singing. As they near the school, his classmates get cold feet seeing Master Bromeley standing alone, but Dobson assures them that the London gentlemen have just gone to see the 'Chancellour shrine of S. *Cuthbert*'.³⁷

At this point things do not seem to go quite to plan for Dobson. After the pupils arrive, Master Bromeley bolts the door and enquires as to why they had neglected to come to school and had not followed Dobson's example in coming to see him first, whereupon the scholars explain what Dobson has done. Fearing a beating Dobson 'skipped into an old Jake [toilets]... protesting that forth of that place he would not come unless his master would solemnly swear to remit and forgive unto him all offences past', and threatening that, should any harm come to him while down there, he would ensure that the Master was blamed.³⁸ Worried that Dobson has gone mad in his desperation (and also more than a little gullible, it appears), Master Bromeley swears that he will pardon Dobson and a rope is cast down to bring the schoolboy up.

³¹ Alex David, *Renaissance Historical Fiction: Sidney, Deloney, Nashe* (Woodbridge, 2011), 89–99 (e.g. 93); on *Dobsons Drie Bobbes* and the development of the novel see also, Avril S. O'Brien, 'Dobsons Drie Bobbes: A Significant Contribution to the Development of Prose Fiction', *Studies in English Literature, 1500-1900*, 12 (1972), 55-70.

³² David, *Renaissance Historical Fiction*, 92–3; O'Brien, 'Dobsons Drie Bobbes,' 68–9; E.A. Horsman, ed., *Dobson's Drie Bobbes: A Story of Sixteenth-Century Durham* (Oxford, 1955), ix–xvi.

³³ *Dobsons Drie Bobbes Sonne and Heire to Skoggin* (London, 1607), sigs [L4]v–M3r.

³⁴ Elvet Moor House still exists just off the Great North Road about half a mile south of where it meets the road from Durham to Crook: Horsman, ed., *Dobson's Drie Bobbes*, xii.

³⁵ *Dobsons Drie Bobbes*, sig. M2r.

³⁶ *Ibid.*, sig. M2v.

³⁷ *Ibid.*

³⁸ *Ibid.*, sig. M3r.

Byrd's name appears in the jest as a specific detail designed to make Dobson's lies more plausible to his schoolmates. Perhaps too, the name of Byrd and the promise of new music is intended to entice them back, eager to sing the latest works from London's most famous composer. Byrd was not in fact a doctor, but Dobson presumably adds this detail to inflate Byrd's reputation further still. The episode suggests that Byrd's was a name to conjure with, even in a part of the kingdom as remote as Durham.

Like Dobson's classmates, the reader is surely expected to know who Byrd is in order to understand the practical joke that Dobson is playing and how wittily he is deceiving his fellows. However, a knowledgeable reader may have understood further layers to this story if they were aware of Byrd's position as a practising Catholic serving in Elizabeth's Protestant Chapel Royal. As literary scholar Alex David has noted, the post-Reformation disruption at Durham Cathedral is pointedly absent from the world of *Dobsons Drie Bobbes*, despite its 1560s setting.³⁹ James Pilkington was appointed bishop of Durham in 1561 (the period in which Dobson exploits are set). He ordered the bells of the collegiate church of St Andrew Auckland to be smashed and removed officials to replace them with more ardent reformers. His wife supposedly burned the banner of local saint, St Cuthbert. Such was the local disquiet regarding these reforms that one of the major acts of the Northern Rebellion of 1579 was to occupy Durham Cathedral and to restore altars and images in local churches.⁴⁰ David reads the absence of this religious turbulence from *Dobsons Drie Bobbes* as creating 'a myth of an Elizabethan "Merrie England"', free from religious controversy and emphasising continuity and tradition.⁴¹ David even suggests that reference to Byrd's music was intended to be indicative of that harmony within the cathedral.⁴²

However, given Byrd's Catholicism, the reference to the composer and his music is not a straightforward marker of social or religious harmony. Indeed, the evocation of Byrd is one of a number of Catholic undercurrents in this particular jest. In suggesting that the gentlemen from London are visiting St Cuthbert's shrine, Dobson equates them with pilgrims; the gentlemen are religious conservatives, if not Catholics. Moreover, Dobson's whole jest depends on the traditionally Catholic notion that there is a saint's day to justify the holiday and even Master Bromeley acknowledges the possibility that there might be such a day 'either by the prescript of the Church or the general custom of the Country' and has to check the day and time of year to ensure that this is not the case.⁴³ In this context, the fact that the gentlemen have brought Byrd's music specifically may not be solely related to his pre-eminent status as royal composer, but also to Byrd's position straddling religious divides: serving in the royal household of a Protestant Queen but equally embedded in England's traditional Catholic past through attending clandestine services and composing music for the Catholic liturgy.⁴⁴ Indeed Dobson's suggestion is never that Byrd's music will be sung in the cathedral, but rather just by the boys at the school, perhaps registering a tension between permitted liturgical practice and local sympathies. Either way, Byrd is represented as a foremost London composer whose reputation has spread to the furthest reaches of England, and who despite serving at the royal court, can be readily understood to be associated with traditional Catholicism in the form of saints' days and shrines.

Finally, I will briefly explore one slightly later jest which on first reading also appears to relate to William Byrd and a fellow musician, but in fact turns out not to do so. This jest appears in *The Booke of Bulls* (1636). Again, this jest is short enough to quote in full:

A Captaine in the *Low-Countreys* being in the company of one, who was a very

³⁹ David, *Renaissance Historical Fiction*, 93–4.

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*, 94–5.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*, 97.

⁴² *Ibid.*, 98.

⁴³ *Dobsons Drie Bobbes*, sig. M2r.

⁴⁴ See for example, Kerry McCarthy, *Byrd* (Oxford, 2013), chaps. 5, 11, and 13.

goodly and a properman demanded his name, and learning that he was named *Bird*; hee said, this is not that *Bird* whom *Taverner* kil'd, is it?⁴⁵

This example is symptomatic of a brief fashion for a particular type of jest c.1636–38: the bull. Bulls were verbal slips—involuntary or deliberate—that result in nonsensical or paradoxical statements. Bulls could be either intentionally funny or unintentional signs of foolishness or lack of understanding.⁴⁶

While the text here is not so explicit that ‘Bird’ is the composer of that name, the combination of two names associated with musicians—Byrd and Taverner—conjures up associations with musicians in the mid-seventeenth century. While the composer John Taverner had died over 90 years ago, he was still being cited in published lists of English masters of music, as in *Wits Common Wealth* (1634).⁴⁷ Equally, in 1636, the name Taverner might also have brought to mind the John Taverner who was currently serving as Professor for Music Gresham College, a post he had held since 1610, delivering free lectures on music to a diverse audience of merchants and citizens in London.⁴⁸

The bull element of the anecdote, however, does not rely on any association with music. Rather, the nonsensical element lies in asking the living person you are being introduced to whether they are the same person as one you know to have been killed. The names of Byrd and Taverner are not part of the humour here as they were in the Byrd/Woodcock jest. There does not seem to be any particular pun around the name of Taverner—someone who keeps a tavern—and birds.

Moreover, while the cause of Byrd’s death in 1623 is unknown, he certainly was not killed by John Taverner the composer (who died in 1545), and there is no reason to think he was killed by the Gresham Lecturer either.

There was, however, a legal case in 1614 in which a Richard Taverner was tried for the murder of one John Bird. In 1609, Bird had challenged Taverner to a duel of swords over an unpaid debt. The duel took place in Theobalds Park during which Taverner killed Bird. Taverner initially fled to the continent but returned to England in 1615 and was subsequently tried for murder in 1616. The incident was recorded in the State Papers because it was included in the news that Londoner John Chamberlain conveyed to Dudley Carleton in February 1609 and the case was still being cited in the nineteenth century as establishing that it was murder if the challenged party killed their rival in a dual.⁴⁹ The protagonists of this newsworthy incident seem a more likely Bird and Taverner to be known to a captain in the Netherlands than the musicians of these names, and make more sense of the bull’s reference to killing. While the incident occurs several decades before *The Booke of Bulls* was published, this is true of some of the few other bulls in which names individuals occur, including one naming John Bull as Gresham Lecturer of Music, a post he had not held since 1607.⁵⁰ William Byrd is almost certainly not the ‘Bird’ referred to in this particular jest.

Yet what are we to make of Byrd’s two earlier jestbook appearances and how might they help us to make sense of a seventeenth-century mindset that could comfortably attribute a drinking catch to the composer? What links Byrd’s catchbook appearance with the two jestbook cameos in

⁴⁵ A.S. Gent, *Booke of Bulls*, 20–21.

⁴⁶ Lucy Munro, ‘Richard Brome and *The Booke of Bulls*: Situating *The New Academy*, or *The New Exchange*’, *The Ben Jonson Journal*, 13 (2006), 125–38, at pp. 128–9.

⁴⁷ Francis Meres, *Wits Common Wealth: The Second Part* (London, 1634), 639; copying directing from Frances Meres, *Palladis Tamia: Wits Treasury* (London, 1598), f. 288v.

⁴⁸ See, John Taverner, *On the Origin and Progress of the Art of Music*, ed. Joseph Ortiz, *Music Theory in Britain, 1500–1700: Critical Editions* (New York, 2018).

⁴⁹ John Chamberlain, ‘Chamberlain to Carleton. April 30, 1616. MS SP 14/86 f.281’, Records Assembled by the State Paper Office. The National Archives (Kew, United Kingdom) *State Papers Online* <<https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/MC4323684189/SPOL?u=unn&sid=bookmark-SPOL&xid=9402ec30>>; John Chamberlain, ‘Chamberlain to Carleton. April 30, 1616. MS SP 14/86 f.281’, Records Assembled by the State Paper Office. The National Archives (Kew, United Kingdom), *State Papers Online* <<https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/MC4323684189/SPOL?u=unn&sid=bookmark-SPOL&xid=9402ec30>>; William Snyder, *Great Opinions by Great Judges: A Collection of Important Judicial Opinions by Eminent Judges* (New York, 1883), 11–14. See also Lloyd Bowen, *Anatomy of a Duel in Jacobean England: Gentry Honour, Violence and the Law* (Woodbridge, 2021), 192–3.

⁵⁰ A.S. Gent, *Booke of Bulls*, 84.

Dobsons Drie Bobbes and *Tarltons Iests* is that these publications both place Byrd in a more playful and humorous context than other sources and spread his reputation further through society than most of his music publications would have reached. While *Dobsons Drie Bobbes* was somewhat longer than *Tarltons Iests* (56 folios compared to 24), it was nevertheless still relatively short and printed in the same blackletter type that ensured the widest possible readability. Playford's catchbooks also envisaged a wide audience. Catches represented the simplest form of part-singing and while sightreading from the books would require musical literacy, taking part in the singing did not as such short songs could be readily learnt by ear. Hilton and Playford's catchbooks were regularly reprinted and expanded over the seventeenth century, each time reproducing Byrd's name in association with 'I Have a Jolly Tankard'.⁵¹ Indeed both jests and catches enjoyed considerable breadth of audience, crossing boundaries of class, blurring distinctions between learned and popular entertainment, and traversing written versus oral dissemination. It seems likely that portrayals of Byrd in media such as these had wider reaching impact on perceptions of the composer than those found in manuscript inscriptions, theory treatises, conduct literature, or the prefaces of music prints.

Moreover, these appearances of Byrd in the context of popular forms of entertainment are an indication of the pervasiveness of his reputation and the familiarity of his name beyond the courtly and elite circles who may have had direct contact with the composer and his music. The image of Byrd that was being projected in the popular imagination upheld his status as a preeminent composer of his day—and indeed relied on this—but for those who met Byrd in the pages of jestbooks or as the author of a drinking catch he is less likely to have appeared as the composer 'naturally disposed to gravity' described by Peacham or the staid and pious composer often

represented in most modern scholarship. Indeed, in the seventeenth century, as drinking culture became increasingly associated with royalist, anti-puritan sentiments,⁵² Byrd's association with drinking catches may have seemed all the more plausible, in a nostalgic or conservative way that is perhaps not so dissimilar to Dobson's use of Byrd to nod to conservative religious custom.

The 'real' person of Byrd is as lost to us as it was to most of the jestbook audiences and Playford's catch singers. Yet Byrd's appearance in such mirthful contexts should give us pause to reconsider the potential significance of some of Byrd's more light-hearted compositions in his sixteenth and seventeenth-century reception. Pastoral partsongs such as 'Though Amaryllis Dance in Green', 'Who made thee Hob Forsake the Plough?', and 'Come Jolly Swains', and even Byrd's early contributions to the English madrigal—the two versions of 'This Sweet and Merry Month of May' and 'The Fair Young Virgin', the latter also published with the Italian text, 'La virginella'—have still received relatively little critical attention,⁵³ which is likely to be at least in part due to the difficulty of reconciling them within our received image of Byrd. However, such pieces may not have seemed so peripheral to his reputation for those who had encountered Byrd's name in the context of jests and catches. Afterall, Byrd always claimed in his song publications to provide music for all humours, including the 'merrie' and those 'of myrth'.⁵⁴

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⁵¹ See above note 4.

⁵² On which see Stacey Jocoy, 'The Role of the Catch in England's Civil Wars', *Essays on Music and Culture in Honor of Herbert Kellman*, ed., Barbara Haggh (Paris, 2001) 325–34.

⁵³ A recent exception is Jeremy L. Smith's discussion of the pastoral songs in *Verse and Voice in Byrd's Song Collections of 1588 and 1589* (Woodbridge, 2016), though he aims to show their potential political readings and literary qualities, rather than embracing a lighter vein in Byrd's output.

⁵⁴ William Byrd, *Psalmes, Sonets & Songs of Sadnes and Pietie* (London, 1588), 'The Epistle to the Reader'; *Songs of Sundrie Natures Some of Grauitie, and Others of Myrth* (London, 1589), title page; *Psalmes, Songs, and Sonnets* (London, 1611), 'To all true louers of Musicke'.

A Musical Enigma

The Baroque Bass Recorder

Isobel Clarke and Douglas MacMillan

The number of extant Baroque bass recorders greatly exceeds the number of parts assigned to the instrument in contemporary compositions. This conundrum raises intriguing questions about the use and distribution of bass recorders: who were the makers and players of these instruments, what kind of music was played upon them and in what context? In this study, we shall examine the organology of the bass recorder, the geographical distribution of its makers, relevant iconography, and assigned repertoire.

A search of repertoire, inventories, sales and purchases relating to the bass recorder in the period 1670 to 1800 culled substantially from David Lasocki's *Not just the Alto* (2020) and other literature (noted below) indicated that the heyday of the Baroque bass lay in the late seventeenth and early eighteenth centuries, with a marked decline in references after c.1740.¹ Lasocki's volume presents a comprehensive account of recorder scholarship covering recorders other than the alto in the period 1600–1800, including both paragraphs and tables on the bass and documenting its usage, particularly in France (see below). Matters covered included organology, repertoire and usage, details of sales, purchases and (often inaccessible) societal data. Musical instruments exist to be played and the essential question, in the case of the Baroque bass recorder, is 'why are there so many instruments yet so little repertoire?' After studying the instruments, their repertoire, and iconography, we shall look at their possible use in a continuo role and indulge in a degree of speculation as to the possible uses of the instrument by amateur musicians – whose activities are seldom reported – and discuss the evidence for and against this hypothesis, drawing on Baroque playing practice and iconographic material.

The Organology of the Baroque Bass Recorder

The Baroque bass recorder evolved from the almost-cylindrical Renaissance recorder in late seventeenth century France. Although the bore is commonly described as 'cylindrical', Adrian Brown and David Lasocki point out that, within this generalisation, there are both mildly conical, cylindrical, and step bores.² Although the recorder in f is frequently called 'bass', using modern terminology it should strictly be styled 'basset' but, for the purposes of this article, we will use the more commonly used term 'bass' for the instrument.³ Great, contrabass, and sub-bass recorders in c, F and C (again employing twenty-first century recorder terminology with Helmholtz pitch notation) were essentially instruments of the sixteenth and early seventeenth centuries and not of significance in the late Baroque era.

Baroque bass recorders first appeared around 1660.⁴ The instruments are approximately one metre long and have a more contracting conical bore compared to the Renaissance recorders and this change in bore profile has the effect of not only lowering the pitch of the instrument but also allowing the tone-holes to be placed closer together to the greater convenience of the player.⁵ Most Baroque basses are sounded by blowing through a crook (or bocal) inserted into the side or top of a cap which covers the block, although a very few are edge-blown: the use of a crook enables a greater flexibility in playing position, as end-blown instruments have to be played vertically between the player's knees.⁶ A strut may be fitted to the foot joint to support the weight of the instrument, particularly should the player be standing.

¹ David Lasocki, *Not just the Alto*, (Portland, Oregon, 2020), tables B, C, D (pp.37–49).

² Adrian Brown and David Lasocki, 'Renaissance Recorders and their Makers.' *American Recorder* 47/1 (January 2006), pp.19–31.

³ It should be recalled that the term 'flute' (in various languages) referred to the recorder in the late seventeenth and eighteenth centuries. See Lasocki, *Not just the Alto*, p.13, for a list of the terms applied to bass recorders.

⁴ David Lasocki, *Jean-Baptiste Lully and the Flûte: Recorder, Voice Flute, and Traverso*. French Baroque *Flûte* Series, no.2, (Portland, Oregon: Instant Harmony, 2019), p.60.

⁵ Stewart Carter (ed), *A Performer's Guide to Seventeenth-Century Music*, rev. Jeffrey Kite-Powell (Bloomington: 2nd. edn, 2012), p.74.

⁶ For example, an instrument by Christian Schlegel (fl.1712–46) in CH.B.hm (100.1879) is cited by Philip T. Young, *4900 Historical Woodwind Instruments* (London, 1993), p.211.

Illustration 1 - Bass recorder attributed to Bressan, GB.O.ub 0114. (With Permission of the Bate Collection, University of Oxford.)

Illustration 2 - Foot of the Bressan bass recorder showing the F key, bulbous foot-joint, side vent, and supporting strut. (With Permission of the Bate Collection, University of Oxford.)

All Baroque bass recorders have a key to bring the seventh tone-hole within the reach of the player's right little finger but, with the advent of the crook, the instrument could be held obliquely and the protective fontanelle covering the key(s) of the Renaissance recorder became redundant. Some examples by the Dutch maker Thomas Boekhout (1666 – 1715) were furnished with additional keywork for the third hole, principally to improve the comfort of the player and facilitate the intonation of the octaves c'–c'' and d'–d''.⁷

Although the compass of the bass recorder is two octaves from f, the notes above d'' are weak but a significant acoustic problem with Baroque recorders is that their lowest register also tends to be weak and lack power, a matter of particular importance for the player of a bass line. Recorders tend to sound to the ear rather lower than their actual pitch because the tone is strong in the fundamental and second harmonics, the higher harmonics being weak. Instruments required to play the bass part in an ensemble need a strong lower register, and unfortunately Baroque recorders tend to be deficient in this respect. This is a matter of some importance when considering

the bass recorder both as the bass of the recorder consort and as a possible continuo instrument: the problem was addressed to some extent by the English makers Peter Jaillard Bressan (1663–1731) and Thomas Stanesby sr. (c.1668 – 1734). Their instruments were discussed by Eric Halfpenny in two articles dating from 1955 and 1962.⁸ Commenting on three instruments by Bressan, Halfpenny notes:

‘There is a side vent in the foot-joint [which is bulbous and expanded – authors] with a strut below it. Is the strut just a support or does it have an acoustic function? The bore ends in an ivory socket into which the strut (which is hollow and open to the bore) is fitted. It probably acts as a resonator to strengthen the lower notes’.⁹

Halfpenny comments that the tone is stronger with the strut in place. The Stanesby instrument has a conventional bell but with an elongation of the bore and an expansion of the bore below the seventh hole, again to increase the power of the lower register.¹⁰ A French drawing of an early

⁷ Jan Bouterse, *Dutch Woodwind Instruments and their Makers 1660–1760* (Utrecht, 2005), p.28.

⁸ Eric Halfpenny, ‘The Bass Recorders of Bressan’, *The Galpin Society Journal*, 8 (1955), pp.27–31; ‘Technology of a Bass Recorder’, *The Galpin Society Journal* 15 (1962), pp.49–54.

⁹ The Bressan recorders are preserved in GB–Chester, Grosvenor Museum (O.S.25c); GB–Norwich (NWHCM: 1942.66.SH16); GB–London, Victoria and Almert Museum (293-1882).

¹⁰ GB–Warwick, County Museum (M16).

eighteenth-century bass recorder reveals a bulbous foot with a side vent, no doubt with a similar intention.¹¹ Nevertheless the majority of Baroque basses had a conventional bell and foot-joint although a solid mechanical supporting strut may be found on instruments by other makers including Boekhout.¹²

Even with these modifications, the fact remains that the bass recorder is a soft instrument.

Surviving Baroque Bass Recorders and their Geographical Distribution

Nicholas Lander's online compilation of extant historical recorders currently lists some almost 2,000 recorders held in collections world-wide and, mainly from this database, we have identified 103 Baroque basses whose maker and current location can be established with certainty.¹³ Of interest, bass recorders represent 17% of surviving seventeenth- and eighteenth-century recorders of the Baroque type.¹⁴ The geographical location of the makers of these recorders reveals an interesting pattern, which may or may not necessarily reflect the usage of the instruments: on a balance of probabilities, the numbers of extant instruments in any given location might be expected to give some indication of their usage in that area. This dilemma would be somewhat easier to resolve were there to be a substantial assigned repertoire but, as will be seen, the surviving repertoire for Baroque bass recorders is small.

The chart below (illustration 3) indicates the geographical location of the makers, and from these figures, it would appear that the Baroque bass recorder assumed particular importance in Bavaria,

despite there being apparently little repertoire from that region.

A Note on larger Baroque Bass Recorders

The Baroque-style bass recorders in c, F, and C encountered in twenty-first century practice do not have a significant historical foundation. Great bass recorders (those, for the present purpose, larger than the basset in f) were essentially a product of the Renaissance and only three possible examples of such Baroque recorders have been identified.¹⁵ James Talbot's celebrated manuscript of 1692–5 refers to a 'pedal or double bass' recorder in C, but no English examples of such an instrument are extant; similarly, there are no surviving French examples although Lully writes for *Grande basse de Flûte* in *Le triomphe de l'Amour* of 1681.¹⁶ Although there are occasional instances in the repertoire assigned to the bass recorder where the music extends below f, in the absence of contemporary surviving instruments it must be assumed that players would have made the necessary octave transposition to play the passage on their f recorder.

Iconography

Whilst iconography is of undoubted value in the study of the history of music, its value in organology may be limited, as iconographic representation is not necessarily compatible with organological veracity and, similarly, there is no definitive proof that these pictorial representations are actual representations of performance practice. It must be admitted that iconography—with one notable exception—has been of little value in the study of the role of the Baroque bass recorder.

■ Germany ■ Netherlands ■ France ■ England ■ Other

Illustration 3 - Geographical distribution of surviving Baroque bass recorders.

¹¹ Edward Croft-Murray, 'An Early 18th. Century French Drawing of Wind Instruments', *The Galpin Society Journal* 33 (1980), p. 130.

¹² Jan Bouterse, 'Die Bassblockflöten von Thomas Boekhout', *Tibia* 24/2 (1999), pp.457–462.

¹³ Nicholas S. Lander 1996 – 2022. Recorder Home Page: Instruments. Last accessed 21 June 2022. <https://www.recorderhomepage.net/instruments/>

¹⁴ Lasocki, *Not just the Alto*, p.146.

¹⁵ Bass in c by I. C. Denner, D-Anon., cited by Young, *4900 Historical Woodwind Instruments*, p.60; bass in c by N. Pappe, D-Berlin: William Waterhouse, *The New Langwill Index* (London: Tony Bingham, 1993), p.291; bass in d by I. C. Denner, National Music Museum, Vermillion, USA: André P. Larson, 'Original Bass Recorders in the United States', *American Recorder* 26/4, (1985), pp.171–172.

¹⁶ GB-Och Music MS 1187; Anthony Baines, 'James Talbot's Manuscript', *The Galpin Society Journal* 1 (1948), pp.9–26.

An often-cited engraving of Antonio Lotti's *Teofane* (1719) being performed at the Dresden opera house is said to show three alto recorders, a bass recorder between two theorbos, two flute (traverso) players, and a line of violins: however, an examination of the score shows that two *flauti* (which could have been recorders as opposed to transverse flutes) are required, but there is no suggestion of the presence of a *flauto basso*, or, indeed, of a bass recorder supplying a bassetto to altos as may be found in the late seventeenth and early eighteenth centuries (examples are given below under 'Repertoire').¹⁷

Anonymous images of an early eighteenth-century banquet in Munich and of a ceiling fresco in Prague (1749) both depict rather stylised bass recorders but neither of these images convey significantly accurate information regarding the structure and usage of the instrument.¹⁸ However, the Munich image does suggest the use of a bass recorder with upper strings, although it should be recalled that the lowest note of the bass recorder is f, above the c of the viola: in the light of its pitch, was it functioning as a true bass in the ensemble?

An engraving of a Collegium Musicum in Nuremberg (c.1775) reproduced in François Lesure's *Music in Art and Society* more convincingly shows a bass recorder, viol, and harpsichord making up the continuo section in a cantata with three singers, three violins, two trumpets, and three unidentifiable wind instruments, possibly including recorders.¹⁹

From these sources, we would assert that only the Nuremberg Collegium Musicum unambiguously illustrates the use of a Baroque bass recorder. This image does suggest the possible continuo use of the instrument although the year of its printing comes at a time when the recorder was becoming obsolete but, as the only image of the bass recorder as a

continuo instrument, it would be inappropriate to dismiss the evidence it presents.

Repertoire

We return to the enigma: 'why do so many bass recorders survive in comparison with the small extant contemporary repertoire?' It is not within the scope of this article to give a comprehensive list of all the pieces for which a bass recorder may be played: we have chosen examples which we consider provide an overview of the assigned usage of the Baroque bass recorder in France, England, and the Germanic lands.

France

The most extensive orchestral deployment of the Baroque bass recorder is to be found in late seventeenth-century French writing, most specifically in large-scale sacred and theatrical music by Jean-Baptiste Lully (1632–87) and Marc-Antoine Charpentier (1643–1704), both composers exploiting the instrument as bass to a recorder group and on occasion taking the third line in an instrumental ensemble. Comprehensive coverage of this repertoire is given by David Lasocki in his *Jean-Baptiste Lully and the Flûte* (cited above, note 4) and his *Marc-Antoine Charpentier and the Flûte: Recorder or Traverso?*²⁰ This author presents a readily-accessible summary of the French repertoire in *Not Just the Alto*.²¹

In the interests of verbal economy in the present article, we have selected four illustrative pieces by Lully, two by Charpentier, and one by Michel Pignolet de Montéclair.

The *Prélude* to Act V Scene 1 of Lully's *Alceste* (1674, LWV 50) uses a bass recorder (*basse de flûte*, F4 clef, range f–f1) as a bass to two alto recorders, the recorder group alternating with a string ensemble.

¹⁷ D–DI Mus. 2159-F-7. The engraving is shown in Douglas Alton Smith 'Sylvius Leopold Weiss', *Early Music* 8/1, (1980), pp. 47–58: there is no suggestion in this article that the woodwinds are recorders but Adrienne Simpson advances this theory in *The Cambridge Companion to the Recorder*, ed. John Mansfield Thomson (Cambridge, 1995), p.96

¹⁸ Nicholas S. Lander. 1996 – 2023. Recorder Home Page: Anonymous: 18th. century. Last accessed 9 January 2023 <https://www.recorderhomepage.net/recorder-iconography/anonymous-18th-century/>; 'Banquet' (early 18th century), Munich: Bayerische Staatsgemäldesammlungen, Inv. 13280. Musicians play three violins with a bass recorder; 'The Heavenly Feast of the Just' (1749), ceiling fresco, Siard Nosecký (1693-1753). Prague: Královská kanonie premonstrátu, Summer Refectory. Amongst other instruments, there is what looks like a bass recorder (though possibly a sordun).

¹⁹ François Lesure, *Music and Art in Society* (Pennsylvania, 1968), plate 8.

²⁰ Lasocki, *Jean-Baptiste Lully and the Flûte: Recorder, Voice Flute, and Traverso* (see n4); David Lasocki, *Marc-Antoine Charpentier and the Flûte: Recorder or Traverso?* (Portland, Oregon: Instant Harmony, 2015, 2nd. ed, 2018).

²¹ Lasocki, *Not Just the Alto*: see Tables B and C (pp.37–40, the Bass Recorder in works by Lully and Charpentier; see pp.150–9 for a discussion of the French repertoire for both bass and other recorders.

Example 1 - Prelude to Act V Scene 6 in *Aleste*. The bass line is marked flûtes. (© The British Library Board, shelfmark I.306.j., p.178).

Two years later, bass recorders were required in *Atys* (LWV 53).²² The choruses 'La beauté le plus sévère' and 'L'Hymen seul ne saurait plaire' (Act IV Scene 5) have parts for five *flûtes*, the bass recorder (C3, g-c1) taking either the bass line in a three-part ensemble or the third line in a quartet. The composer's *Tragédie-comédie et ballet Psyché* of 1678 (LWV 45) has parts for a bass recorder (F4, G-c1) in the opening *Plainte italienne* which comprises six flute parts with the option of strings. In the aria 'Deh, piangete al pianto mio' and in the final *Rondo des Enseignes* the instrument provides a bassetto to two alto recorders.²³

Towards the end of Lully's ballet *Le Triomphe de l'Amour* (1681, LWV 59) the *Prelude pour l'Amour* forms a late and unusual example of the use of a four-part recorder/German flute consort, for the German flute had only recently been redeveloped in its Baroque form and its use alongside the more established *flûte à bec* is of interest.²⁴ The parts are distributed between vertical and transverse flutes:

1. *Tailles ou flutes d'Allemagne*
2. *Quinte de flutes*
3. *Petite basse de flutes*
4. *Grande basse de flutes et basse-continue*

The upper two parts are uncontroversial but the third line (with a compass of a-a') lies comfortably on a basset recorder in f, forming an example of the use of this instrument in an inner part. The bass line (F4, D-d') is interesting on two grounds, firstly that there are no extant French Baroque great basses (*Grande basse de flutes*) in C or D and, even so, the instrument was a considerable rarity in the Baroque. Secondly, the only note below F is one occurrence of D, but this could easily be transposed up an octave on a bass in f without having a catastrophic effect on the music. As the bass line also involves a keyboard continuo, it seems reasonable to speculate that the player of the recorder in f would simply play the part as written (and thus sounding at 4-foot pitch) whilst the keyboard provided an 8-foot bass.

Charpentier's curious *Messe pour plusieurs instruments au lieu des orgues* (1674, H.513) contains five sections to which recorders are assigned, including a *Kyrie* for mixed recorders and German flutes with four bass recorders (F4, A-c1) on the bass line.²⁵ *Quoniam tu solus sanctus* from the *Gloria* requires *une octave et une flute douce* (sopranino and alto recorders) doubling the first and second parts, *basses de flute* (F4, A-c1) on the fourth part, with a third part for a *cromorne* playing divisions on the bass line. The recorders all participate in the concluding *Offerte à deux choeurs*.

Charpentier's taste for the bass recorder clearly endured, as his later the opera *Medée* (1694, H.491) has five sections for a *Basse de Flutes* playing with realised continuo (the bass is figured) in recorder-trio passages, as well as including a bass recorder part in a five-part prelude with two recorder and two violin parts.²⁶

A considerably later work by Michel Pignolet de Montéclair (1667–1737) is worthy of mention as a late example of the use of the Baroque bass recorder in France. His opera *Jephthé* of 1732 includes five-part ensembles for *flûtes* written in the G1 clef but, of greater interest in the present context, *Basses de Flûte* (F4, A flat-c1) accompany two *flutes*, recalling the earlier practice of bass recorders providing a bassetto to two altos in the aria 'Quel bonheur' (Act V, Scene 6).²⁷

Lully essentially abandoned the use of the consort of recorders around the time of the development of the Baroque recorder in the 1660s.²⁸ Subsequently, it appears that the prime use of the Baroque bass recorder in late seventeenth and early eighteenth centuries France lay in playing in a small contrasting group within the orchestral ensemble for specific occasions or sonic effects rather than a 'full-time' member of the band, and, in this capacity, the bass recorder most often formed a bass to smaller recorders.

²² Jean-Baptiste Lully, *Atys*, GB-Lbl G.1544.ii.

²³ Jean-Baptiste Lully, *Psyché*, ed. John S. Powell and Herbert Schneider (Hildesheim, 2007).

²⁴ Jean-Baptiste Lully, *Le Triomphe de l'Amour*. GB-Lbl K.7.i.1.

²⁵ Marc-Antoine Charpentier, *Messe pour plusieurs instruments au lieu des orgues* (Tours: La Sinfonie d'Orphée: vol.5, 2004).

²⁶ Marc-Antoine Charpentier, *Medée*, Editions du CNRS, (Paris: 1987).

²⁷ Michel Pignolet de Montéclair, *Jephthé*: GB-Lbl L.309.c; the flute parts may be intended for recorders or transverse flutes. Lasocki opines that the *flûtes* would be transverse instruments (*Not Just the Alto*, p.158).

²⁸ Lasocki, *Not Just the Alto*, p.150.

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Ah! Cruel Fate, Ah! Cruel Fate, thus to oppose my

Flutes

Flutes

Soft.

Love.

Soft Murmurs issue from the

Flutes

Detailed description: This is a page of handwritten musical notation on aged paper, numbered 56 in the top right corner. The page features several staves of music. The top staff is a complex, multi-measure passage with many beamed notes. Below it is a vocal line with the lyrics "Ah! Cruel Fate, Ah! Cruel Fate, thus to oppose my". The middle section contains three staves: the top one is labeled "Flutes" and has a few notes; the second is also labeled "Flutes" and has a few notes; the third is a complex, multi-measure passage with many beamed notes, labeled "Soft.". Below this is another vocal line with the lyrics "Love." and "Soft Murmurs issue from the". The bottom staff is labeled "Flutes" and has a few notes. The paper shows signs of age, including some staining and wear at the edges.

Example 2 - 'Surprizing change' from *Pan and Syrinx* (autograph). The bass line is marked 'Flutes'. (© The British Library Board, shelfmark Add MS 31588, p.56).

England

The orchestral use of the bass recorder in England follows a similar pattern to that seen in French music from the same period – which is not surprising, given the influence of French tastes upon English mid-Baroque compositional styles.

John Blow (1649–1708) wrote parts for ‘2 Flutes and a Base Flute’ in his orchestral anthem for strings and SATB voices *Lord who shall dwell in thy tabernacle* of c.1680–4.²⁹ The alto recorders and a bass recorder are the only woodwind instruments in this anthem, the bass recorder providing a bass to the two altos. The part has a ridiculous range of C–f: the few notes below F could be transposed up, but the rather exposed passages calling for f’ would be uncomfortable (if not unplayable) on a late seventeenth-century English bass recorder. Herein lies the first of several episodes we shall encounter demonstrating that composers were not always cognisant of the capabilities of the instrument. It has been suggested that the part should be played on a great bass recorder to obtain the lower notes: however, the use of such an instrument would render the upper reaches of the part inaccessible.

Henry Purcell’s *Hail! Bright Cecilia* of 1692 (Z.238) presents a further example of a bass recorder providing a bass to two altos in an orchestral setting. The duet ‘Hark! hark! each tree’ (No.3) for soprano and bass is littered with rapid changes in the orchestral accompaniment, with phrases for the ‘recorder trio’ being interspersed with sections for two violins and bass violin. The use of a bass recorder is not entirely without controversy as the part does extend to E although this phrase could easily be transposed up an octave.³⁰ The bass recorder is not specified in all contemporary versions of the score: the autograph (1692) specifies a bass flute although the 1694 version omits this direction, and at least two authors have addressed the question.³¹ Such use of the bass recorder mimics Lully’s writing in the ‘Marche de

Melpomene’ from *Les Fêtes de l’Amour et de Bacchus* of 1672 (LWV 47).

The German-born London immigrant Johann Ernst Galliard (1687–1747) made similar use of the bass recorder in an aria from his opera *Pan and Syrinx* (1717). Following the text note in Scene nine ‘Here the Scene Represents Syrinx Transform’d into Reeds’, Pan (bass) sings the aria ‘Surprizing [*sic*] Change’. His aria opens with an instrumental introduction for viola obbligato and *basso continuo*, to which two alto recorders and a ‘bass flute’ are added. This particular bass part is unfigured, probably indicating that the keyboard should be omitted. Roger Fiske suggests that the sound of the three recorders represents the voice of the transformed Syrinx as she is changed into reeds.³² A parallel may be seen in Lully’s *Isis* (1677, LWV 54), where the recorders are also used to portray the transformed Syrinx.

Our final example of orchestral bass recorder usage in England is found in Handel’s 1737 opera *Giustino* (HWV 37).³³ Here, the *Basso de Flauti* doubles the viola part below two alto recorders to form a bass in a 36-bar instrumental introduction to *Giustino*’s aria ‘Puo ben nascer tra li boschi’. Despite the instruction *senza cembalo*, the continuo bass line is figured: the bass recorder part is notated in the alto (C3) clef, with an ambitus of F to d’.

In addition to its orchestral role, there is substantial evidence for the use of bass recorders in chamber ensembles and, from the English repertoire, pieces utilising alto and bass recorders without keyboard accompaniment are of interest, not least because they show a poor perception on the part of composers of the compass and limitations of the bass recorder. It should be noted that a piece for (say) *Two Flutes and a Bass* does not necessarily imply a bass recorder unless the latter is specifically mentioned in the title or in the part.

²⁹ John Blow, ‘Lord, who shall dwell in thy tabernacle’, ed. Bruce Wood, (London: Musica Britannica Trust, 1684), pp.49–68.

³⁰ According to Talbot’s manuscript, ‘pedal basses’ existed in England in the late seventeenth century. The use of such an instrument would solve the problem of the low notes but could prove problematic in the higher passages.

³¹ GB–Obl MS Mus.c.26; GB–T G.517.yy; Walter Bergmann, ‘Henry Purcell’s Use of the Recorder’, *The Recorder and Music Magazine* 7/12 (1983), pp.310–313; Christopher Hogwood, Preface to *Ode on St. Cecilia’s Day*, (Mainz: Edition Eulenberg 8063 (2009), p.v.

³² Roger Fiske, *English Theatre Music in the Eighteenth Century*, (London, 1973), p.60.

³³ HWV 37; GB–Lbl H.229.c (published by John Walsh, 1737).

Example 3 - Title page to *An Excellent Solo for a Flute and Bass* by Seignr. Papus. (© The British Library Board, shelfmark c.105.a(1.), title page).

The London firms of John Walsh and John Hare published extensively for amateur recorder players in the early eighteenth century: however, a number of their publications do not mention a bass recorder in the title but have the heading 'FLUTO BASSO' across the top of each page of the bass part. Their 1702 arrangement of parts of Arcangelo Corelli's opus 5 sonatas forms an example:

Six Solos for a Flute and A Bass...being the second part of his Fifth Opera... The whole Transposed and made fit [*sic*] for a Flute and a Bass with the approbation of several Eminent Masters.³⁴

The parts are headed *Fluto Primo* and *Fluto Basso*. The latter part has an extended compass of D–e' and contains some tricky semiquaver passages, to say nothing of the necessity for some octave transposition. The bass line is figured (unlike, for example, the bass part in the Papus/Pepusch solo for a Flute and Bass of 1704, cited below),

suggesting that the bass recorder player provided a melodic continuo line together with a keyboard instrument.

In 1704, Walsh published *Six Sonatas of Two parts ... for two Flutes compos'd by William Croft. To which is added an excellent Solo for a Flute and Bass by Seign: Papus*.

'Papus' is identified as Johann Christoph Pepusch (1667–1752), the notable German composer who spent most of his life in England. The bass part headed *Fluto Basso* is unfigured and apart from occasion occurrences of D fits neatly on the bass recorder.

The bass recorder is specified in the title page of J. C. Pepusch's *A Second Set of Solos for the Flute with a Through Bass for the Bassoon, Bass-Flute or Harpsichord* (1709), the publisher using 'Bass-Flute' as the contemporary term for the recorder.³⁵ The bass part is figured and headed 'Organo': it would

³⁴ GB-Lbl e.682

³⁵ GB-Lbl h.250.c.(2.).

probably be challenging to many recorder players as there are several incursions into the alto (C3) clef. The sections in this clef require a range of D–b' (well outside that of the bass recorder) and sections in the bass (F4) clef require C–e'. However, most of the part lies within a comfortable range for the bass recorder although, realistically, a keyboard assisted by a bassoon would seem a better option. In the anonymous *New Aires made on Purpose for two Flutes and a Bass Familiar & Proper for Practitioners in*

Consort (1712) the unfigured bass part is headed 'Bass Flute': with occasional octave transpositions to avoid the use of e', f', E, D, and C, the part lies within a comfortable range for the instrument.

As in orchestral writing, the bass recorder is providing a bass to alto recorders rather than taking the bass part in a sixteenth-century style recorder consort of four or five recorders.

Example 4 - Bass flute part from *New Aires made on Purpose* (© The British Library Board, shelfmark H.17.(1).), p.1.

Germanic Lands

We have seen that over half of the surviving Baroque bass recorders were made in Germany and it comes as something of a surprise to find that, at least in comparison with France and England, there is apparently little assigned repertoire. The instrument mainly appears (as in other traditions) as the bass to recorder ensembles within an orchestral setting but pieces specifying 'bass recorder' (in various translations) are few and far between: the use of the bass has to be deduced by a part in the F4 (or, rarely, C3) clef in a recorder group.

Typical examples are provided by two extracts from works by the organist and composer Michael Rohde (1685–1732). His aria 'Jesu, Jesu, mein Regiere' has parts for two alto recorders (*Flute doux* 1 and 2) and a bass (*Fluto*) notated in the F4 clef with a range of F to d' with very occasional excursions to E at the cadence points. A similar arrangement of parts pertains in the composer's 'Jesus ist mein Aufenthalt'. In both arias, the bass recorder forms a bass to two alto recorders and doubles the continuo line: when the recorders are silent, the organ accompanies alone.³⁶ The romantic aria 'Süsse Lippen, holde Wangen' of Johann Peter Guzinger (1683–1773) requires four recorders: the four parts are assigned to *Flauto 1*, (etc.), the fourth part being in the F4 clef with a range of F to b flat, doubling the keyboard at the octave.³⁷

One of the five extant compositions by Johann Christoph Faber (dates unknown) is a miniature suite in the French style *Parties sur les fleut douce à 3* for alto, tenor, and bass recorders without keyboard.³⁸

Turning to more significant figures, we find that both Georg Philipp Telemann (1681–1767) and Johann David Heinichen (1683–1729) had occasional use for the bass recorder. Telemann called for a 'Flauto basso' in his *Trauer-Actus Über die Nicht-und Flüchtigkeit des menschlichen Lebens*

(TVWV 1:380, c.1697–1701).³⁹ This early work requires a choir of SATB singers, a choir of four violas da gamba, and a choir of four recorders (two altos, tenor, and bass) with continuo. The bass part is designated *Flauto 4 basso o Fagotto* and has a compass of F–b; the instrument is assigned to provide a bass to the other recorders in four of the seven movements, including an instrumental ritornello in which only the recorders play.

Heinichen's serenata *Zeffiro e Clori* (1712–16, S.202) calls for three alto recorders and a bass recorder in the aria 'Mira le me, pupille'.⁴⁰ There is no keyboard part, the bass line being sustained either by the bass recorder (*Basso de Flauto*) or pizzicato double basses. The compass of the bass line (E flat–e flat') is problematic as it falls outside the range of the standard bass recorder in f. On a larger scale, the composer's Concerto in G, S.215, is scored for two *flauti* and *basso di flauti*, two oboes and bassoon, with five-part strings and continuo.⁴¹ The *basso di flauti* provides a bass to the two alto recorders in their 'solo' passages, as does the bassoon to the oboes, and the 'cello to the violins.

More familiar to recorder players is Carl Philipp Emmanuel Bach's Trio Sonata for viola, flauto basso, and continuo, written in Berlin in 1755. Four versions of the work survive, but only two involve the bass recorder: H.588/Wq163 in F for *viola, flauto basso e cembalo* and H.589 in B flat for *fagotto obbligato, flauto basso e cembalo*.⁴²

The work is unique in its instrumental assignments, and it is most probable that the *flauto basso* is a recorder in f, the compass of the part being F–c' (notated). Lasocki translates Bach's note that 'The bass recorder (*Bassblockflöte*) goes from f0 to c2; F major, C major, and G major are the most comfortable keys for it'.⁴³ The compass and texture of the part strongly suggests a bass recorder and, when performed with a degree of sensitivity on period instruments, there is no reason to suppose that the recorder would be inaudible against a viola.

³⁶ S–L Sammlung Wenster Ä:23, F:16; modern edition, Peter Thalheimer and Klaus Hofmann (Herbipol), *Flauto e voce IV* (Stuttgart: Carus 11.16, 2000).

³⁷ Cited in Lasocki, *Not just the Alto*, p.193

³⁸ Cited in Lasocki, *Not just the Alto*, p. 195.

³⁹ D–Dl Mus.2392–E–551.

⁴⁰ D–DS Mus.2398–L–6; cited in Lasocki, *Not just the Alto*, p.192.

⁴¹ D–DS Mus.ms.240/6; S.215.

⁴² D–Bsb Mus.ms.Bach 357; B–Bc MSM 27.896.

⁴³ Lasocki, *Not Just the Alto*, p.196 and n853.

Example 5 - Opening of C. P. E. Bach H.588/Wq163 Trio for viola, flauto basso e cembalo. (IMSLP, Public Domain).

Curiosities defying Classification

Andrew Robinson postulated that recorders may have been played in 'choirs' during the earlier years of the eighteenth century.⁴⁴ He based his argument on the existence of oboe bands and on documents detailing orders for 'choirs of recorders' from the Nuremberg maker Jakob Denner in 1710 and in 1720. In 1710, The Duke of Gransfield (Nuremberg) ordered four *Flauten*, one *Alt-Flaute*, and two *Bass-Flauten*, and in 1720 Göttweig Abbey (Krems, Austria) received a similar choir of six recorders (again with two basses) which remain in the monastery's collection.⁴⁵ There is no record of the repertoire played on these instruments.

Alina Madry and Patryk Frankowski report a *Harmonia pastorella in D* by Francisek Perneckher which includes a part for a 'concertato bass recorder', but no other instrumentation is

described in their RILM abstract.⁴⁶ The piece dates from 1755–69.

An unusual *Concerto de Flauti* by Alessandro Marcello (1669–1747) preserved in Venice is scored for *due flauti soprani e due sordini, due flauti contralti e una violetta sordina, due flauti tenori et una violetta sordina, un flauto basso e violoncello*.⁴⁷ *Due sordini* implies two muted violins. There are effectively four choirs in this unique concerto comprising SATB recorders and strings, the upper strings muted to match the softer recorders. The bass recorder doubles the 'cello throughout, the compass of the part being G–d'.

A lost trio by Carl Heinrich or Johann Gottlieb Graun with an obbligato bass recorder part has been speculatively reconstructed by Klaus Hofmann in the manner of the C.P.E. Bach trio discussed above.⁴⁸ As an ingenious reconstruction,

⁴⁴ Andrew Robinson, 'Families of Recorders in the late 17th and 18th. Centuries' *Recorder Magazine*, 23/4, (2003), pp.113–117; 24/1, (2004), pp.5–9.

⁴⁵ Philip T. Young, *Die Holzblasinstrumente im Oberösterreichischen Landesmuseum*, (1994), p.59.

⁴⁶ Alina Madry and Patryk Frankowski, 'Perneckher's *Harmonia pastorella* and C. P. E. Bach's trio in F: A rare example of compositions for concertato bass recorder', RILM accession 2012716376.

⁴⁷ I–Vnm Ms.It.IV, 573.

⁴⁸ Klaus Hofmann, 'Gesucht: Ein Graunisches Trio mit obligater Bassblockflöte. Ein Ermittlungsbericht—mit Seitenblicken auf ein Trio Carl Philipp Emmanuel Bachs', *Tibia* 17/4 (1992), pp.253–262.

the piece requires at least a mention in the present article.

Conclusion

The prime documented use of the bass recorder in the late seventeenth and early eighteenth centuries was playing as a bass to two alto recorders, such an ensemble being employed as a small group within an orchestral setting for specific (often pastoral) effects although there is also some evidence in the English repertoire to indicate its use as a melodic continuo instrument. There remains the enigma of a profusion of instruments despite little assigned repertoire, leading us to speculate that bass recorders may have been used as continuo instruments, particularly in the largely undocumented sphere of amateur music-making.

However, there are what we might call ‘technical’ problems with this theory. Although the bass recorder tends to sound lower than the listener would expect, its lowest note is only a fifth below middle C, and, in comparison with the standard melodic continuo instruments, it is essentially lacking in terms of pitch and range. The standard melodic continuo instruments (the ‘cello, the bass viol, and the bassoon) all have a compass of over two octaves from around two octaves below middle C: they pose few problems of audibility and are capable of considerable dynamic flexibility. Considering the characteristics and capabilities of the average Baroque-period instrument, the bass recorder could hardly be said to fulfil the criteria for a continuo instrument, despite being an appropriate bass to a pair of alto recorders.

In discussing the bass recorder’s failings as a potential continuo instrument in this context, we are essentially looking at it as a ‘professional’s instrument’. Here, we move from the realms of verifiable fact into the shady territory of speculation. Thus far, the evidence is contradictory:

we have a large number of surviving instruments dating from the mid to late Baroque period, which is indicative of a certain level of popularity. At the same time, assigned parts in orchestral and ensemble music are relatively few and far between, and certainly nowhere near numerous enough to account for the manufacture of so many bass recorders. The most likely scenario seems to be that the bass recorder was used as a continuo instrument in domestic music-making, and we propose three main reasons underlying this speculation.

Firstly, it is known that the recorder had already been popular as an amateur’s instrument for several decades with a substantial published repertoire and pedagogical material. Playing a continuo line on the bass recorder would have been a relatively straightforward undertaking for the skilled amateur. Secondly, this type of *ad lib.* instrumentation was positively encouraged by publishers at the time and, as we have seen, there is substantial printed evidence that, at least in England, the bass recorder was considered a viable domestic continuo instrument. Thirdly, it seems logical that the trend of using a bass recorder to provide continuo for two alto recorders in theatrical works might be reproduced in domestic contexts, for example in trio sonatas for two recorders and keyboard.

Is there substantial evidence for this practice beyond the repertoire examples, one image, and our speculation? The only answer is ‘very little’, and despite applying such evidence as may be deduced from multiple sources there remains much that is enigmatic about the Baroque bass recorder, but at least our studies have highlighted the status of an elegant instrument within an historical context.

Isobel Clarke and Douglas MacMillan

New Theatre Airs by William Croft at Urbana

Peter Holman

The project initiated many years ago by RISM (Répertoire Internationale des Sources Musicales) to catalogue music in the series A/ii, Music Manuscripts after 1600, has now been combined with information about printed music into the database *RISM Catalog*, which is freely available online <@>.¹ This increasingly valuable resource is continuing to throw up new sources of English eighteenth-century music, particularly in hitherto under-explored American libraries. A good example is a set of part-books of theatre music at the Music Library of the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, US-U, MO15633. To judge from the description posted in *RISM Catalog* (best accessed by typing its RISM ID no. 1001159459 into the search box), it consists of eight bound part-books entitled 'Musica / de / la Theatro' on at least one of the covers, with parts for oboe 2 (oboe 1 is missing), 2 horns, bassoon, two violins, viola, bassoon and violoncello, and basso continuo. I am grateful to Michael Talbot for alerting me to the collection, and to Kirstin Johnson, the Head of the Music and Performing Arts Library at Urbana-Champaign for answering my queries and for providing me with a digital copy of the item to be discussed below.

Research into this fascinating collection has hardly begun (it would clearly be a good subject for a major research project, perhaps as a Ph.D. thesis), though we can see from the RISM listing (and from an index in the basso continuo part-book) that the collection consists of 82 numbered sets of parts, printed and manuscript, many incomplete, for instrumental pieces or the instrumental accompaniments of vocal pieces. The composers, evidently mostly working in the London theatres, range in date from those active in the late seventeenth or early eighteenth centuries, including

Henry Purcell, John Eccles, John Weldon and (we shall see) William Croft, to those evidently writing for productions put on in the London theatres in the second half of the eighteenth century. These later items include: 'Ye spotted snakes' (no. 26) from J.C. Smith's Shakespearean opera *The Fairies*, produced at the Drury Lane Theatre on 3 February 1755;² music by William Boyce for the pantomime *Harlequin's Invasion, or A Christmas Gambol* (nos. 81 and 82), produced at the Drury Lane Theatre on 31 December 1759;³ and the overture to Galuppi's comic opera *Il filosofo di campagna* (no. 69), first performed in Milan in 1751 and first produced in England at the King's Theatre in the Haymarket on 6 January 1761 – this may be the latest piece in the collection.⁴ Other composers mentioned in the RISM list for the collection include Thomas Arne, Jacob Cervetto, Richard Charke, John Ernest Galliard, John Garth, George Frideric Handel (mostly excerpts from his operas and oratorios), Johann Adolf Hasse, John Frederick Lampe and Giovanni Battista Sammartini. Not everything in the collection is theatre music: it also includes a set of manuscript instrumental parts for Henry Purcell's *Te Deum* and *Jubilate in D major Z232* (nos. 39 and 40).⁵

Looking through the list of the collection in the *RISM Catalog*, my attention was immediately drawn to the entry for 'Mr Croft's *Musick in Perollo and Isadora*', no. 74 in the collection. Listed in the index as 'Act Tunes by Dr. Crofts', it consists of four printed parts for two violins, viola and bass (in the basso continuo part-book), with a manuscript copy of the bass part in a much later hand in the bassoon and violoncello part. It is apparently a hitherto unknown (or at least a hitherto unidentified) set of theatre airs by William Croft for

¹ I am grateful to Olive Baldwin, Thelma Wilson, Michael Talbot and Andrew Woolley for their helpful comments on a draft of this article. <@> indicates that the item concerned was freely available online at the time of publication.

² *The London Stage 1660-1800, Part 4: 1747-1776*, ed. G.W. Stone jr (Carbondale IL, 1962), 467; see also R. Fiske, *English Theatre Music in the Eighteenth Century* (Oxford 2/1986), 243-4.

³ *The London Stage ... 1747-1776*, ed. Stone, 765; see also I. Bartlett with R.J. Bruce, *William Boyce: A Tercentenary Sourcebook and Compendium* (Newcastle, 2011; repr. 2013), 128-9.

⁴ *The London Stage ... 1747-1776*, ed. Stone, 836; see also F.C. Petty, *Italian Opera in London 1760-1800* (Ann Arbor MI, 1980), 92-3.

⁵ See H. Purcell, *Servives*, The Works 23, ed. M. Laurie and B. Wood (London, 2013), xxx-xxxii, where the only set of parts listed is GB-Lam, MS 27e, 'Incomplete set of parts, mainly instrumental, early to mid-eighteenth century'.

Colley Cibber's tragedy *Perolla and Izadora*, first produced at Drury Lane on 3 December 1705.⁶

Perolla and Izadora has only been known hitherto from a list of 'Books of Instrumental and Vocal Musick Printed in ye Year 1709' included in a British Library copy of John Walsh's *Monthly Masks of Vocal Music*, where it is just listed as 'Musick in Perollo and Isadora' without the composer being mentioned.⁷ The publication appears to be a previously unknown issue in Walsh's series *Harmonia Anglicana (HA)*,⁸ though this is not mentioned in the Urbana printed parts; Walsh had been using this title to publish sets of theatre airs in collections of six since the 1700–1 theatre season. His practice was to publish them within a few months or even weeks of the first performance of the parent play, so it is likely that Croft's airs for *Perolla and Izadora* (or *Perollo and Isadora*) were actually first published in the spring of 1706 rather than 1709. If so, then the set probably belongs to the *HA* collection Curtis Price labelled 'Collection c', containing airs for plays produced mostly at Drury Lane in the theatre season 1705–6; no newspaper advertisement for the publication seems to have survived.

Perolla and Izadora brings the total of Croft's known sets of theatre airs to five; it is the only one written for a tragedy rather than a comedy. They were all composed for plays produced at Drury Lane and were all published by Walsh in *HA*. The others are for David Crauford's *Courtship A-la-Mode*, produced on 9 July 1700, with the airs published the following year in *HA*, Collection I, no. 3;⁹ for Richard Steele's *The Funeral, or Grief A-la-Mode*, produced in December 1701, with the airs published almost simultaneously in *HA*, Collection III, no. 2;¹⁰ for George Farquhar's *The Twin Rivals*, produced on 14 December 1702, with the airs

published in *HA*, Collection V, no. 3 in January 1703; and for Steele's *The Lying Lover, or The Ladies Friendship*, produced on 2 December 1703, with the airs published in *HA*, Collection VI, no. 3 later that month.

Perolla and Izadora is almost the last evidence of Croft's involvement with Drury Lane. After John Blow's death in 1708 he succeeded his former teacher as organist of Westminster Abbey, master of the children of the Chapel Royal and composer to the queen, subsequently devoting himself largely to church music. A song 'I hate a fop, that at his glass', setting words from Act III of Thomas D'Urfey's comedy *The Modern Prophets, or New Wit for a Husband*, produced at Drury Lane on 3 May 1709, was attributed to Croft when it was published that month.¹¹ However, it is labelled 'Written by M^r Durfey the Tune by M^r Croft', and it turns out to be a mock-song based on the second movement, 'Aire', of the *Perolla and Izadora* airs; D'Urfey was fond of writing mock-songs, adding words to existing music.¹² So it seems that Croft did not compose the song for the play, and that *Perolla and Izadora* was indeed Croft's theatrical swansong.

Croft's airs for *Perolla and Izadora* consist, as was the norm at the time, of nine movements. A fine overture in E minor is followed by five movements, 'Aire' (2), 'Jigg' (3), 'Courant' (4), 'Gavott' (5) and 'Aire Slow' (6), also in E minor, then a 'Roundo' (7) in E major, and two movements in A major, an elaborate 'Allemand' (8) and a 'Jigg' (9). Nine movements in a set of theatre airs provided for, in addition to the overture, four movements played in two groups as the First Music and Second Music before the play began, and four movements serving as entr'actes or act tunes between the five acts of the play. It was not necessary for all the movements to be in the same

⁶ *The London Stage 1660–1800, Part 2: 1700–1729 a New Version, Draft of the Calendar for Volume 1, 1700–1711* [LSNV], comp. and ed. J. Milhous and R.D. Hume, 258; this valuable resource, formerly freely available online, is now incorporated into *Eighteenth-Century Drama: Censorship, Society and the Stage* <<https://www.eighteenthcenturydrama.amdigital.co.uk>>.

⁷ W.C. Smith, *A Bibliography of the Musical Works Published by John Walsh during the Years 1695–1720* (Oxford, 1948; repr. 1968), 98, 101–2 (no. 314).

⁸ Listed in C.A. Price, *Music in the Restoration Theatre, with a Catalogue of Instrumental Music in the Plays 1665–1711* ([Ann Arbor MI], 1979), 237–43.

⁹ Modern edition: W. Croft, *Music in Courtship A-la-Mode*, ed. B. Clark (Centelles, 2003); a critical edition will appear in *Restoration Theatre Airs 1660–1710*, ed. P. Holman and A. Woolley, Musica Britannica (forthcoming).

¹⁰ Modern edition: W. Croft, *The Comedy Call'd the Funeral: Suite for Strings and Continuo*, ed. R. Platt (London, 1976).

¹¹ *The Monthly Mask of Vocal Music, 1702–1711, a Facsimile Edition*, ed. O. Baldwin and T. Wilson (Aldershot and Burlington VT, 2007), no. 269. For the play, see LSNV, 486–7.

¹² See *The Songs of Thomas D'Urfey*, ed. C.L. Day (Cambridge MA, 1933).

key since, unlike conventional suites, they were not played in a continuous sequence. In the theatre the overture would have come fourth, after the First and Second Music, but, as with this set and all other published sets of theatre airs, the movements would have been shuffled for publication to place the overture first and to make a satisfactory key sequence for concert and domestic performances. We do not know what the original order of movements was in the *Perolla and Izadora* set, though it is possible that the pair of A major movements (nos. 8 and 9) originally formed the First Music: the Allemand would have made an impressive start to the sequence in the theatre.

More light on the *Perolla and Izadora* set is provided by a number of concordances of its movements in other manuscript and printed sources; I am grateful to Andrew Woolley for identifying them and for providing me with a list. All the movements are found in untitled and unattributed four-part versions in the Magdalen College Part-Books, GB-Cmc, F.4.35 (1–5), a set organised by key into 60 numbered sets and copied by the French bassoonist and prolific music copyist Charles Babel (d. 1716).¹³ These concordances are as follows:

Table 1 - Concordances between *Perolla and Izadora* (PI) and the Magdalen College Part-Books (MCPB)

<i>PI</i> , no.	Title	Key	MCPB, Set/no.
1	Overture	e	XIII/1
2	Air	e	XIII/5
3	Jigg	e	XIII/7
4	Courant	e	XIII/3
5	Gavott	e	XVI/13
6	Aire Slow	e	XIII/4
7	Roundo	E	III/14 (in E _b)
8	Allemand	A	XVII/12
9	Jigg	A	XVI/13

In addition, there are keyboard versions of nos. 5 and 7 in Croft's autograph, GB-Och, Mus. 1141a, ff. 7v and 7r respectively, where no. 7 is entitled 'Slow Ayre';¹⁴ as well as a version in G major of the outer parts of no. 7 in GB-Lbl, MS Mus. 1852/5, f. 145v, a pair of treble and bass part-books also

copied by Charles Babel and entitled by him 'Concerts a deux'.¹⁵

I am also grateful to Andrew Woolley for pointing out that nos. 8 and 9 appear in keyboard settings in Jeremiah Clarke's posthumous collection *Choice Lessons for the Harpsichord or Spinett* (London, 1711), nos. 6 and 8,¹⁶ and therefore we might think that these two movements are actually Croft's arrangements of keyboard pieces by Clarke. The Allemand, with its flowing semiquavers in the outer parts, certainly looks like an arrangement of a keyboard piece, though the ensemble version of the Jigg appears to have been composed first, since each strain starts with a series of contrapuntal entries, the second neatly inverting the subject of the first; the keyboard setting consists of just the outer parts, omitting these essential inner parts (see Ex. 1, at the end of the article).

That, of course, does not prove that Croft rather than Clarke wrote these two pieces, though an incorrect attribution in a posthumous keyboard collection is perhaps more likely than one made in *Harmonia Anglicana* at a time when Clarke (d.1707) was still alive to object to Croft's plagiarism.

As for the dates of the manuscript concordances, Rebecca Herissone gives c.1705 for the Magdalen College Partbooks in her catalogue of Restoration music manuscripts,¹⁷ not knowing the concordances with the *Perolla and Izadora* airs, though Babel could easily have compiled his collection a few years later than that, and the same is true of Croft's autograph keyboard settings of two of the pieces in GB-Och, Mus. 1141a, which Andrew Woolley dated 'c.1702 or slightly later' largely on the basis of the presence of keyboard settings of three pieces from Croft's airs for *The Twin Rivals*. However, Charles Babel seems to have completed the copying of his 'Concerts a deux' at the end of 1702 or the beginning of 1703: the last suite in the collection, no. 65, includes some pieces from James Paisible's airs for Colley Cibber's comedy *She Wou'd and She Wou'd Not*, produced at

¹³ See esp. R. Herissone, 'The Origin and Contents of the Magdalene College Partbooks', *R.M.A. Research Chronicle* 29 (1996), 47–95.

¹⁴ A. Woolley, 'An Unknown Autograph of Harpsichord Music by William Croft', *Music & Letters* 91 (2010), 149–70.

¹⁵ They formerly belonged to Christopher Hogwood as GB-CAMhogwood, M1092; see A. Woolley, 'English Keyboard Sources and their Contexts, c.1660–1720', Ph.D. thesis (University of Leeds, 2008), 205–10 <@>.

¹⁶ Edited in J. Clarke, *Seven Suites*, ed. J. Harley (London, 1984), 6–7, 8.

¹⁷ See R. Herissone, *Musical Creativity in Restoration England. Appendix: Catalogue of Restoration Music Manuscripts* <@>.

Drury Lane on 26 November 1702;¹⁸ this set was published by Walsh in *HA*, Collection V, no. 2, advertised on 15-17 December 1702.¹⁹ Therefore, no. 7 in the *Perolla and Izadora* airs may have been composed by Croft a few years before the rest of the set.

All in all, the discovery of Croft's airs for *Perolla and Izadora* provides us with a notable addition to the repertory of English early eighteenth-century string consort music; I hope to investigate the sources more fully and to publish an edition of it in due course. More generally, the 'Musica de la Teatro'

collection at Urbana demonstrates that some Restoration theatre music continued to be of use half a century or more after it was written. It certainly has the potential to add greatly to our knowledge of eighteenth-century English theatre music, and it will doubtless keep those interested in the subject fruitfully occupied for many years to come.

Peter Holman

Example 1 - William Croft, Jigg, no. 9 from the Airs for *Perolla and Izadora*, compared with the keyboard setting in Jeremiah Clarke, *Choice Lessons for the Harpsichord or Spinett*.

The image displays a musical score for a piece titled 'Example 1'. It consists of two systems of music, each with four staves. The top two staves of each system are for a string consort (treble and bass clefs), and the bottom two are for a keyboard instrument (treble and bass clefs). The key signature is one sharp (F#) and the time signature is 6/8. The first system shows the original string consort setting by Croft, with a double bar line and repeat sign at the end of the first measure. The second system shows the keyboard setting by Clarke, which is a more elaborate arrangement of the same piece, featuring a more active bass line and a more complex treble line. The notation includes various rhythmic values, accidentals, and articulation marks like slurs and accents.

¹⁸ *LSNV*, 80. I am grateful to Andrew Woolley for this information.

¹⁹ Price, *Music in the Restoration Theatre*, 222, 240.

Anne Martin, *William Byrd: Consort Music* (Hebden Bridge: Peacock Press, 2023). Paperback, 304pp. ISBN: 9781914934537, £27.50.

The fourth hundred anniversary of William Byrd's death was, both by design and coincidence, a fruitful year for Byrd scholarship. Conferences, concerts, and publications were planned and released to mark the momentous occasion, and they were joined by new studies about the composer's work also published in the same year. As a result, the anniversary of Byrd's death provided scholars with an invitation to reflect on the state of Byrd studies as a discipline, to consider what has been studied, what has been relegated to the margins and, more importantly, what lays ahead. The attention that academics have given (and continue to give) to Byrd's vocal music guarantee that the composer's choral works still remain an important subject within the discipline. His instrumental contributions to sixteenth and early seventeenth century England, however, are more difficult to place in scholarship.

Recently, John Bryan described Byrd's consort repertory as 'the Cinderella of [the composer's] creative output' and with good reason: the surviving thirty-three consort works have remained in the margins of the discipline. The first analytical study of Byrd's consort music was not published until 1978 in a book by Oliver Neighbour that also discussed Byrd's keyboard compositions. Since then, there has been a slow stream of publications that discussed individual works within the consort repertory. Like puzzle pieces, the articles and book chapters that discussed the fantasias and consort versions of Latin motets, like *In manus tuas*, have slowly provided us with a more comprehensive understanding of the repertory. But despite the collective efforts of both performers and musicologists over the last five decades, the puzzle is by no means complete. Perhaps for that very reason, any new scholarship dedicated to Byrd's consort music constitutes an important contribution to the discipline.

Anne Martin's monograph, exclusively dedicated to analysing the thirty-three fantasias, variations, *In nomines*, dances, and consort-versions of Latin motets, is ambitious. Influenced by Neighbour's seminal study published more than forty years ago, the book aims to be a comprehensive publication

featuring musical analysis, commentary, and discussion of sources for each of the surviving consort pieces. The book also aims, with different degrees of success, to place Byrd's consort music within a musical tradition influenced by the education of choristers in Reformation England, to explain performance and composition concepts such as compass and range and how they can affect our understanding of consort music, and to provide an in-depth discussion of the difficulty of analysing Byrd's consort pieces within the confines of tonality or modality. An entire chapter of the book is also dedicated to an extensive discussion of primary sources, which is also continued in the different case studies. Although an important part of the book is dedicated to the primary sources, it does not offer any new insights on what the sources might tell us about Byrd's patrons or the performance of his music at their homes. Instead, the book offers a localised place where manuscript numbers, dating, locations, and some general data about the sources are readily available to review.

The second half of the book is dedicated to the musical analysis of consort music excluding the instrumental settings of Latin-texted motets. The remaining pieces have been organised in a proposed chronological order that aims to take the reader through Byrd's own learning journey as a composer of instrumental music. The chronology begins with the *In nomine* settings, which the author identifies as Byrd's earliest consort works composed before his appointment in Lincoln in 1563, and follows with the fantasias and variations as Byrd's mature works. Some of the pieces are classified as earlier or later works depending on the dating of the manuscript sources, while others have been dated through a stylistic analysis. The importance placed in the proposed chronology suggest that, by the end of the book, the reader should be left with an understanding of what separates his early works from his later ones, how his understanding of the capabilities of the viol evolved and informed his compositions through the years, and how the conventions of music for viols in the sixteenth and seventeenth century were adhered or challenged within the music. And while this is a worthy endeavour, and surely one that is quite necessary for those interested in the instrumental output of the composer, the monograph leaves many of these questions unanswered.

The author approaches Byrd's consort works through a heavy dose of musical analysis with different outcomes. Some analysis, mainly the analysis of the Fantasia G/F and the *Browning Fantasy*, provide an in-depth examination of musical borrowings, influences, use of motifs, structure, and performance challenges that give the reader true insight into these works. That standard is not maintained for the rest of the musical analysis and some of them, such as the discussions of the *In nomine* 4/1 and 4/2, are so short that it is unclear why they are included at all. It is, of course, quite difficult to provide the same level of analysis to every one of Byrd's consort works as some of them are incomplete or they are objectively more complex than others, but perhaps a more discerning criteria in choosing the case studies and what they were meant to demonstrate would have helped to bring all of the analysis to the same standard. Instead, for most of the works studied in the monograph the analysis feels disjointed: the tallying of motifs in some of the works, the pie charts tallying compass and range in the third chapter, and even the discussion about specific counterpoint choices, such as the leaps of a sixth in the *In nomine* 5/5 (where 'Byrd really comes into his own'), feel out of place when the analysis is not grounded in larger research questions (i.e. What are the performance challenges for these works? What can they tell us about viol and consort performance in sixteenth-century England? What do these compositional choices tell us about Byrd's journey as a composer?).

Despite the different standards within the musical analysis, Martin successfully situates Byrd's works within the landscape of consort music in sixteenth century England by drawing comparisons between the composer's works and his mentors and contemporaries, such as Thomas Tallis, Alfonso Ferrabosco the Elder, and Robert Parsons. The comparisons made by the author are more prevalent in the works placed earlier in the chronology, with Martin placing Byrd as a student to other composers of the Chapel Royal before leaving for Lincoln in 1563. The chronology of these influences is a little unclear as it is quite possible that, for example, Byrd had been influenced by Ferrabosco after joining the Chapel in 1572, as his appointment coincided with the longest stretch of time that the Italian composer spent in England before he left the country in 1578. The comparisons between Byrd and his mentors and contemporaries dwindles in the later chapters

of the book where the author discusses the more mature works, providing a narrative of the composer as the authority in consort music of the late sixteenth and early seventeenth century. It is quite possible that continuing those comparisons between Byrd and the younger composers of consort music would have helped to identify his compositional voice as a mature composer at the turn of the century and truly convey the composer's achievements in the genre.

As a result, this monograph is a collection of case studies linked by a chronological order that aims to show William Byrd's evolution as a composer of consort music. The author has chosen to do this through a series of musical analysis that fall in a spectrum between the superficial and the comprehensive. Perhaps a more substantial conclusion to the monograph, showing a reflection of Byrd's compositional language, an understanding of the performance challenges brought by the works, and even a reflection on possible performance purposes (domestic, courtly, didactical) would have helped to bring these analysis together to offer a new alternative to Oliver Neighbour's seminal work that would truly convey that Byrd had 'a comprehensive understanding of the possibilities of the viol.'

Dr Alexandra Siso

The Choir of Chichester Cathedral, Charles Harrison, Rose Consort of Viols. *What Joy So True: Anthems, Canticles and Consort Music by Thomas Weelkes*. Regent Records, REGCD571. 2023.

The 400th anniversary in 2023 of the death of Thomas Weelkes (1576-1623) occasioned a number of fine new recordings. The small but vivacious Chichester Cathedral Choir of fourteen boys and six men performs both familiar and not so well-known anthems and canticles in the very cathedral where Weelkes was organist and choir-master for most of his career. The choir performs both a capella and accompanied by organ or viol consort. (Weelkes did not write any music for choir and viols, but John Bryan has sympathetically and convincingly reconstructed several pieces from incomplete organ scores for viol consort accompaniment.) Weelkes's only two surviving organ solos, played with precision and freshness by Thomas Howell, and pavans and *In nomine* settings

for viols, beautifully performed by the Rose Consort, provide welcome changes of colour to the somewhat unyielding choral sound.

Weelkes's music does not always reach depths of emotion or daringness; nevertheless, there is a stained-glass clarity and directness in the best of his music. Choir director Charles Harrison brings out these qualities well, with rhythmic vitality to the fore. The choir is at its best in the lively pieces ('All people, clap your hands', 'Rejoice in the Lord'), whilst the slower and more expressive pieces ('Lord to thee I make my moan', 'O Jonathan') would benefit from warmer sounds and longer lines. The solo singing in 'Most mighty and all knowing Lord', richly accompanied by viols, is especially lovely, providing a rare intimate moment in the programme.

Balance is problematic. The overall choir sound is rather diffuse and disconnected, with the boys' voices over-prominent. From the photo in the booklet, it appears that the twenty singers are standing in a tight block of short rows behind the five viols. Perhaps arranging singers and viols in a more generous circular formation would have resulted in an integrated and balanced sound, whilst capturing more of the cathedral's very resonant acoustics.

Dr Nancy Hadden

William Byrd at Lincoln: A Symposium Commemorating the 400th Anniversary of the Composer's Death, 3-4 July 2023, Lincoln Cathedral

The Symposium was well-attended by both academics and lay persons and was held in the cathedral's Chapter House. This location lent something of a frisson for the assemblage, in its physical sense of connection with Byrd. A downside, though, was the acoustic - despite the presence of a PA system, coverage was patchy and at times made speakers hard to hear.

After a welcome to all participants, the first afternoon session began with two papers under the title *Byrd at Lincoln*, chaired by Owen Rees. Magnus Williamson's remarks on '*The Acoustic Environment of Byrd: Lincoln Minster in the 1560s*', started the proceedings. He traced the disposition of the Lincoln cathedral organ prior to 1702, when

the then instrument was erected on the mediaeval choir screen. Before that there had been several organs at various periods, Darby's organ was, as in Hollar's 1670 depiction on the north side of the quire, in the first bay west of the eastern crossing. He related positions of the sequence of instruments, along with changes in the fabric of this part of the cathedral as a response to the requirements of 'semi-dramatic liturgical performance [which suggests that] Byrd's Second Service, long reckoned a Lincoln work, was therefore composed for a distinctive disposition that modern performances seldom convey.' Choirs then seem to be much more mobile than now, in order to adorn the liturgies.

Thomas Wilson then continued with "*A Nest of Unclean Byrds*" – *William Byrd, Lincoln Cathedral Chapter, and Archdeacon John Aylmer's "purge" of Lincoln Cathedral*. An account of 'changes in the Cathedral's religious milieu during Byrd's time'. He had to navigate the shifting tides of both persuasions. This prompts thoughts of how Byrd adapted to the swirling changes in acceptable liturgy, and particularly music, in his sojourn there. Using Aylmer, the Archdeacon of Lincoln, who was chosen to lead a commission in to 'outlawed rituals' this paper explored the tensions between Protestant and Catholic sympathies and the balance of these matters within the cathedral chapter – and the sympathies for a nuanced usage of both ideas which Byrd favoured, along with Queen Elizabeth I. Aylmer apparently boasted that he had 'purged Lincoln Cathedral' – after his commission, the Precentor and Subdean 'were deprived for their Catholic sympathies'. The atmosphere at the time was beset by officious zealots often with axes to grind.

The second panel, 'Byrd and Recreational Song', was chaired by Katherine Butler. The first paper was *Nec doctum satis: Humanist Translation and English Recreational Song* given by Joseph M. Ortiz, where analysis of English Renaissance madrigals—possibly unconsidered in past musicological endeavours in favour of more 'serious' genres—was employed to attest to the humanist nature of such works. The extent to which recreational song texts can be an appropriate vehicle for 'serious' study was positioned as a key question in the paper, as well as that there was a contemporary debate concerning the extent to which recreational song was given some prominence by Thomas Weelkes

in *Ayres and Phantasticke Sprites* (1608) – ‘... whose classical references have seldom been seriously considered.’

Katie Bank, one of the conference’s convenors, followed with *William Byrd’s ‘Woeful Orpheus’ in Context: Motion as visual and musical affect*. This focussed on a singular work by Byrd, ‘Come, woeful Orpheus’ (1611). By further reference to the Orpheus overmantel, in Haddon Hall, which lies some 3km south-east of Bakewell in Derbyshire, some elements of musical and visual culture together were employed to illuminate, as Bank put it ‘[a reciprocity] between somatic and symbolic cues within the domestic sphere’. This led to an understanding of the shared roots derived from ‘classical sources on decorum and persuasive oration. Bank suggested that ‘the physical and visual contributions of performers are crucial to understanding Byrd’s song’. Serendipitously, a ensemble from the cathedral Lay Clerks were on hand to provide a excellent live performance of the song.

The second day began with a panel entitled *Byrd and the Chapel Royal*, containing three papers and chaired by Walter Kreyszig. Andrew Johnstone’s paper surveyed *Byrd’s ‘Association’ with Established Religion*, where he addressed the change in understanding, beginning from Fellowes’ work, of the twists and turns of Byrd’s religious observance, whilst holding to his recusant status as a Catholic. In this, the now greater understanding of the composer’s navigation of the Chapel Royal’s regulations in a markedly delicate manner. Johnstone referred to Byrd’s texts, and contemporary writings by Catholic apologists, to explore how Byrd’s conscience fared whilst serving a Protestant monarch.

Following this was *Confessional Colleagues? Byrd and his contemporaries in the Elizabethan Chapel Royal*, given by Oscar Patton. This paper took, as it’s starting point, the Chapel Royal’s richness in both performance and composition in the period of Byrd’s joining. It enabled Byrd to give actuality to his compositional prowess. Patton noted that only two Catholics can alongside Byrd worked in the Chapel in the period 1538-1603, with others, from the Dean down the roll-call, holding a ‘distinctly Reformed identity’. This enabled a context for this vital period in Byrd’s professional activities.

The session concluded with Alexandra Siso on *William Byrd and the Elizabethan Tabernacle*. Here Siso

took the text of Psalm 14: *Domine quis habitabit in tabernaculo tuo* as an example of settings by several composers ‘... to give voice to one unified message’, in a manner which would be readily understood by both Catholics and Protestants. It was argued that Byrd’s 9-voice setting of the psalm employs the complexity of symbolism which prompts important ties between tabernacle and court. Siso analysed the sense in which this motet could provide advice – and warning – imply that only proper behaviour would enable access to the private elements of the court and the monarch.

The next session, *Performing Byrd: Past and Present*, was chaired by Katie Bank and began with a paper from Joseph Sargent: *Byrd Orchestrated: Three Case Studies*, where it was demonstrated how later composers had produced their own ‘take’ on Byrd’s work. Sargent contrasted twentieth- and twenty-first-century orchestral ‘takes’ on Byrd compositions. This began with Granville Bantock’s *Old English Suite* (1909), and the Leopold Stokowski’s reshaping of a *Pavan and Gigue* (1937). Sargent finished the examples with Nico Muhly’s *Two Motets* (2007). Despite some personal trepidation from this author at the resurrection of the first two, the whole experience was fascinating. Stokowski evidently regarded the Byrd pieces as opportunities to showcase his own mellifluous style; whilst playing down the sense of national and Tudor style. Bantock’s essay speaks to the Edwardian sense of settled national pride. Seemingly the most successful was Muhly’s enabling of Byrd’s musical character, without allowing the contemporary setting to obscure the originals.

The second part of this strand consisted of a recital of Byrd keyboard music performed on the harpsichord with great aplomb and meticulous phrasing by Friederike Chylek. The assembled members of the symposium reacted with thunderous applause. This recital at, more or less, the centre point in the proceedings, enabled the musical practice of Byrd’s work to be brought to the fore.

The recital programme comprised the following:

Prelude, BK12
Fanatsia, BK13
Pavan: Ph. Tregian, BL 60a
Galliard, BK 60b
Callino Casturame
O mistress mine
Hornpipe

The penultimate session, *Byrd's Sacred Music – Motets and Magnificats*, was chaired by Kerry McCarthy and started with Walter Kreysig upon the subject: *Magnificat and Magnificat Antiphon in the Oeuvre of William Byrd at Lincoln and Beyond: from the Anglican to the Roman Catholic Traditions*. This was followed by Owen Rees with: *'That worisbb, that Devlillisbe, and faithlesse Song': Byrd's Salve regina in Context*. The use of the *Salve Regina* was anathema in Protestant England. Rees argued, however, that it was used, in a fashion discrete and covert, along with other Catholic items. John Merbecke was opposed to the use of the *Salve*, though Forrest's *Salve* motet of 1571 was possibly used for private devotions. Unsurprisingly, a certain turmoil in religious observance marked this period. Nevertheless, Byrd's setting of the *Salve* was fully published. That he was able to do this without apparent comeback might be his use of the *Salve* as to some extent Elizabeth as a proxy for Mary, Queen of Scots.

The final panel of the conference was entitled *Byrd's International and Catholic Connections*, chaired by Samantha Arten. Amy Farnell delivered the first paper of the panel, *A Celebration of the Arrival of Two Priests: The Music at Harlesford House, 15-23 July 1586*. 13 July 1586 saw the arrival in London of Robert Southwell and Henry Garnet from Rome – where they began missionary activities in Protestant England. Their advent was marked by a week of welcome, from 15 July, in Harlesford House, where Byrd played the organ and sang with other musicians. This week was also the Feast of St Mary Magdalen; in other words, problematic in its

Catholic flavour. Amy Farnell's paper enabled consideration of various functions of 'chant, historical pronunciation, instrumentation for Byrd's masses, and a poetic text setting'. And specific attention was drawn to the fact the the assemble for Southwell and Garnet's arrival seemingly included both male and female choristers.

To draw the academic proceedings to a close, Kerry McCarthy in her paper expatiated on *Byrd in the Age of Exploration and Exile*. Though Byrd did not venture beyond England, according to the present state of knowledge, he was influenced by information and discourse about overseas events through his proximity to power at court. Not least an influence on him, through his Catholicism, was 'the ideal of the Counter-Reformation exile, to whom even the most devout recusant was sometimes considered a pale second-best'. These matters—and the fact of sea-going adventure—shaped his life. Kerry McCarthy's exploration of these matters, and Byrd's response to them, was a superb means of rounding off the Symposium and vividly brought Byrd to life. Interestingly, he had his own emigration both through the activities of his brother, and of his son. McCarthy opened in this final session the possibilities in a consideration of Byrd's career from an international perspective.

Following the academic proceedings of the event the Choir of Lincoln Cathedral (joined by the Tallis Scholars in the anthem), sang Choral Evensong in St Hugh's Choir with a full congregation. The initial part of the service, after an introit, saw the unveiling and dedication of a memorial commemorating the 400th Anniversary of the death of William Byrd, placed centrally in the stone flagging of St Hugh's Choir; a fitting way to conclude two days of study into one of England's most important composers.

David Dewar
University of Bristol

Cover image: William Byrd, 'Come drink to me' printed in John Playford, *Catch that Catch Can: or A Choice Collection of Catches, Rounds, and Canons: Being Three and Foure Parts in One. Collected and Published by John Hilton Batchelor of Musick. The Second Edition Corrected and Enlarged by J. Playford* (2nd edn; John Benson & John Playford: London, 1658), 66. (Public Domain, IMSLP.)

